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A study on the vitality of Knowledge Management for e- Governance

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Mrs. Archana Singh,
Research Scholar, Pune

Introduction : “Knowledge is information that changes something or somebody either by becoming grounds of actions or by making an individual (or an institution) capable of different or effective action”. (Peter F Drucker,1998). Since time immemorial management of knowledge has been a practise which is the result as we know our culture well and follow our rituals and know about our Upanishads, or holy books. This passes on from generation to generation in written form or through the written knowledge in form of books etc. the two types of knowledge above said are tacit and explicit knowledge.

The concepts :

Knowledge : The term “knowledge” is one of the more confusing aspects of KM. The terms “information” and “data” are often used interchangeably with the term “knowledge”. In fact they have different meanings. And understanding the differences is essential to doing knowledge work successfully. Knowledge is derived from information. It results from making comparisons, identifying consequences, and making connections. Knowledge also includes judgment and “rules of thumb” developed over time through trial and error. Here is a working definition of Knowledge suggested by Thomas Davenport and Laurence Prusak. (Amrit Tiwana, 2000)

“Knowledge is a fluid mix of framed experience, values, contextual information, expert insight and grounded intuition that provides an environment and framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information. It originates and is applied in the minds of knowers. In organizations, it often becomes embedded not only in documents or repositories but also in organizational routines, processes, practices and norms.

The pathway from data to wisdom includes information and Knowledge as two path breakers which are essential ingredients to travel from data to wisdom. The further understanding of Knowledge can be built using “DIKW hierarchy”. (Jonathan Hey, 2004). The hierarchy

is often referred as Knowledge hierarchy or Knowledge pyramid. DIKW stands for Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom.

Definitions of Knowledge - Authors Knowledge Definitions

Nonaka and Takeuchi (1994)	Justified true belief
Wiig (1994)	Truths and beliefs, perspectives and concepts, judgments and expectations, methodologies, and know-how
Liebeskind (1996)	Information of which validity has been established through tests of proof
Ruggle (1996)	A fluid mix of framed experience, value, contextual information, and expert insight
Allee (1997)	Experience or information that can be communicated or shared
Sveiby (1997)	The capacity for effective action
Davenport and Prusak (1998)	Framed experiences, values expert insights, and contextual information
Fahey and Prusak (1998)	Imbuing data and information with decision-and action-relevant meaning
Leonardo and Sensiper (1998)	Relevant, actionable information based at least partially on experience
Wijnhoven (1998)	Collection of concrete experiences or a set of abstract conceptualizations
Den and Huizenga (2000)	A collection of rules and information to fulfill a specific function
Raisinghani (2000)	Formatted information
Al-hawari (2004)	An object that can be codified, distributed, understood, and applied in order to achieve a

Knowledge Management :

“KM can be defined as a process where knowledge, skills, expertise, communication and collaboration are cared for, administered and steered with skills and wisdom in a goal oriented fashion by using different techniques and technologies.” (Riitta Suurla).

In another equally interesting definition, Knowledge Management can be defined as the ability of an organization to create, share and use the collective knowledge of its products, processes and people to increase workplace productivity and reduce activities that “reinvent the wheel” (Michael Fontaine, Eric Lesser) knowledge is slowly becoming the most important factor of production, next to labour, land and capital

- According to (Nonaka and Hirotaka Takeuchi, 1995), KM theory consists of 7 important activities in the operation to manage the knowledge in an organization which are:

- 1. Create the vision on learning,
- 2. Create knowledge management team,
- 3. Create the learning exchange atmosphere intensely in lower level employees.
- 4. Manage along with goods development product/new methods or develop the work format.
- 5. Emphasize on organizational management of "middle-up-down management)
- 6. Change the organization to (hypertext)
- 7. Create the knowledge network to the outside world.

Gill gives a synthesis of some typical definitions of KM. Gartner Groups considers KM as an integral approach to identifying, capturing, retrieving, and sharing and evaluating an enterprise's information assets; both formalized in databases and informal tacit expertise. On the other hand, Burns (Creative Networks) comments the KM from another perspective considering it as "web thinking", that is lateral thinking emphasizing a network of relationships between pieces of information and between information and people, compared with traditional thinking that is linear and sequential.

e- Governance: Heeks defines the concept of e-governance as "e-Governance is the use of information and communication technologies to support good governance; it moves beyond old IT

in government' models thanks to the new digital connections that ICTs permit."

Need of Knowledge Management in the Government:

Why knowledge needs to be managed in government can be best understood by examining government's structure and functions. Four main characteristics of government drive its KM needs:

- Knowledge is a central resource of the government. Effective functioning of government rests on effective acquisition and dissemination of knowledge.
- Government is a distributed enterprise with similar knowledge requirements spread across the states, districts, and other local governments.
- Frequent transfers of knowledge workers across government departments cause the twin problems of “knowledge drain and demand.”
- Governments need to transform themselves into “anticipatory governments” if they desire to meet the challenges of the emerging E-governance era.

Defining Knowledge for Government : As per Piyush Gupta & Puneet Kalia knowledge for government can be categorized into the following categories

Organizational memory - A collection of best practices, heuristics, process documents and other texts that help define how an organization operates. Fundamental rules, Office orders, Rule book, Office manual, Memorandum etc are examples of Organizational memory.

Intellectual capital - The intangible assets of an organization. These include Best Practices, Learning's, competencies, culture and connections that enable and foster innovation, agility, awareness, adaptation and corporate survival. This type of knowledge is produced during day to day working of the organization across different units and geographies. KM plays a role in mapping, recording, evaluating, stewarding, marketing and growing intellectual capital and knowledge assets.

Personal Knowledge – A KM theme, that stems from an individual's urge for learning,

connecting, organizing and producing knowledge. This type of knowledge is tacit in nature and resides in the minds of the employees. KM provides ways and means to capture such knowledge. Blogging, personal information management and branding are some of the ways to capture and distribute personnel knowledge.

International Status :

- In United Kingdom, for example, e-Envoy whose office was set up in 1999 and replaced by e Government Unit in 2004, introduced the knowledge network in 2000 followed by knowledge enhanced government (KEG).
- A development agency like the World Bank also set up a knowledge management secretariat and has come out with a knowledge assessment methodology (KAM). One of the important reasons for this development has been the emergence of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in the last decade.

Five Phases of the World Bank's Knowledge Management Strategy Implementation

- **Initiation:** Top management's commitment establishment of project implementation committee, organization-wide commitments.
- **Planning** Development of various activities relating to Knowledge creating, sharing and utilizing.
- **Phase Execution :** Implementation of developed KM activities.
- **Phase Four:** Monitoring and planning Review of prior KM efforts Problem identification, Solution development.
- **Phase Five:** Closing Formal establishment of KM department, Appointment of related staff Conducting KM as an organizational routine.

National Status :

Five Myths in Knowledge Management for E-government given by Dr DC Mishra.

1. KM is a fad. It is here to stay whether we call it by this or any other name.
2. KM is not for government. Government being knowledge-based, it is very much for government.

3. KM is not for civil servants. Being knowledge workers, civil servants are very much concerned with KM.
4. KM is not for e-government champions.
5. KM being an integral part of e-government, e-government champions, whether politicians or civil servants, are vitally concerned with it.
6. KM is theoretical discipline. It is a practical management tool, which has tremendous potential for increased productivity and competitiveness.

Guiding Principles for Knowledge Management in E-government in developing countries by Dr. D C Mishra.

- Develop a knowledge management (KM) strategy for the organization Leverage knowledge for all.
- Proceed, step-wise, from simple to the complicated. Adopt modular approach. Do not attempt anything highly ambitious in the initial stages.
- Do not re-invent wheel. Make use of existing knowledge and insights. Undertake knowledge needs assessment. Only then plan the next step.
- Make use of information and communication technologies (ICTs). But do not forget GIGO, garbage in, and garbage out.
- Make use of people, process and technology (PPT) model.
- But do not forget: Computers: fast, accurate, dumb, People: slow, sloppy, smart.
- Prepare a simple and modular knowledge sub-plan incorporating, knowledge management (KM) strategy. Do not use any complicated knowledge management (KM) tool or mechanism that cannot be successfully implemented.
- Include knowledge management (KM) sub-plan in the e-business plan of Ministry /Department. Do not prepare any stand-alone knowledge management (KM) sub-plan. It is more likely to fail than succeed.
- Secure top management support to knowledge management (KM) sub-plan. Remember, no plan can succeed without top

management buy-in. This is to be a priority.

- Demonstrate results. Remember, the best way to convince anyone about practical utility of knowledge management (KM) is to show concrete, verifiable results.
- Review the implementation of knowledge management (KM) sub plan from time to time. Review the implementation of the knowledge management (KM) sub-plan against the following three criteria: Has the implementation of the knowledge management (KM) sub plan resulted in: (a) better decision-making by government.

Conclusion & Recommendation : Managing Knowledge has become the dire need of the society for upgrading the performance and productivity. This has been very well explored and is still being explored in private sector so as to reap the benefits of profit. It is also practiced in most of the developed countries as not only processes become smoother by managing knowledge but the greatest threat in today's date, terrorism can also be curbed with proper management of knowledge at government higher till local level. For a successful e-government it is further recommended that:

- KM should be an integrated approach from central to local level of governance but it can be started with integration at municipal level and slowly and steadily it can go to higher level of governance.
- Change is inevitable at government level so as to compete with the global scenario where OECD countries are continuously working on best practices of KM for e-Governance.
- There is a need of decision support systems for designing new services tailored to citizen needs and suitable for a complex Government scenario (Meo, 2008)
- Indian government is working rigorously towards best e- gov activities but if Knowledge Management is applied right away the processes of e- governance will give more efficient and effective results.

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Quality of Work – Life (With Special Reference to BPO Sectors in Hyderabad)

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INTRODUCTION :

Work Life Balance Strategies in BPO's - BPO stands for Business Process Outsourcing and is "the delegation of an intensive business process to an outside service provider who owns administers and manages it according to a defined set of metrics". BPO is generally for back-end administrative functions that are necessary to run a business but are not a part of the core business.

Striking a balance is the real fulfillment to life. In the rat race of our present day existence, especially in the long working hour's ethos of our industry, we forget to maintain a balance between work and family. The result is devastating: high levels of stress, trauma, and even nervous breakdowns. In the field of organization and work psychology, research agendas tend to be influenced by societal and organizational perceptions of pressing issues. At present, the growth of interest in work-life balance reflects a perception that this is an issue that merits investigation.

Company Profile - Automatic Data Processing (ADP) is one of the world's giants in computerized business solution. It has a blue-chip global client list, and an outstanding track record, for over 60 years. In India, it offers you excellent careers in products Development.RIM and BPO-with the opportunity to work with the very latest technologies/processes, across arrange of platforms, to meet the specialized needs of our 570000 clients, in 125 countries. Amazon.com, Inc. is an American multinational electronic commerce company with headquarters in Seattle, Washington, United States. It is the world's largest online retailer. Amazon has separate websites for the following countries: United States, Canada, United Kingdom, Germany, France, Italy, Spain, Japan and China. It is also expected to launch its websites in Poland, Netherlands and Sweden.. Bank of America India Hyderabad is a big name in itself now. Hyderabad, India is the first location that has been

used by the Bank of America to open a Business Processing Outsource (BPO) center. For this BPO center, the Bank of America has owned a non-bank subsidiary named The Continuum Solution Private Limited. BPO, KPO.

Need of the Study - The main need of this study is to introduce the topic of work-life balance, to explain why it is of contemporary interest, to identify some of the key conceptual and empirical issues and to open up the topic for debate. The need of the study is to know employee's opinion towards the work-life balance condition of BPO's and to highlight the various problems faced by them during their working hours.

Objectives :

- 1) To know workers perception towards the work-life balance condition of BPO's in Hyderabad.
- 2) To know the benefits and programs for the BPO employees and their effects to promote work-life balance.
- 3) To study the work-life balance of the BPO employees and the various problems faced by them while working in the BPO sector.

Limitations :

1. Though the sample size is small, it is assumed to represent the population.
2. Duration of the study was for a period of 3 months which was not sufficient for a detailed study.
3. The study is conducted by taking a limited sample of 100 which may not give a true picture of population.
4. Conclusions are drawn based on the responses of the respondents.

Research Methodology :

The study includes surveys and fact finding studies of various kinds. The major purpose of

this research is description study on the work-life balance of the BPO employees in Hyderabad and it also states the affairs or problems as they exists and are faced at present by BPO employees.

Sampling Design - The study is based on a survey conducted in Hyderabad. It is collected using convenience sampling. The total sample size is 100. Data is collected from three Companies i.e. ADP Company, Amazon.com and Bank of America.

Data Collection - The primary data is collected using a structured questionnaire and personal interview conducted within the organization. The secondary data includes Internet, books on related issues, and research reports of various researchers in relevance to my study.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND SURVEY :

The papers say “Employees are required to ‘manufacture’ relationships...Quite often; aspects such as moods of the agents (employees), facial expressions and words are subject to monitoring. The agents are even found forced to either express some feelings, which they do not feel or suppress certain feelings, which they genuinely want to share. In both the cases, the employees find the job depressing and leading to emotional dissonance”. “Emotional exhaustion adds to the physical and mental strain of the workers, leading to higher levels of stress and burnout under the electronically monitored work and tightly bureaucratized work regime.”

Outsourcing decisions are not, technically, irreversible. But in practical terms the organizational disruption and financial costs of bringing services back in house (“back sourcing”) mean that few organizations revert, even when quite dissatisfied with an arrangement. Instead, organizations typically seek to move to another outsourcing arrangement, that is sometimes less attractive than the original in-house delivery. Preliminary evidence from studies of business process outsourcing (BPO) experiences, like those into IT outsourcing’s success, suggests that only a minority of organizations report their BPO arrangements as satisfactory, implying that many are caught in this “can’t go back” bind. The people who work in these call centers — indeed, in any

company in India — do so out of choice, not coercion. They make that choice on the basis of the options available to them, options which are now far wider than they were a decade ago.

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

CHART 1: CHART REPRESENTING THE REASON FOR JOINING BPO

INTERPRETATION:

According to the above analysis, it can be concluded that 32% of the BPO employees work for reputation, 20% of the employees work to pursue further studies, 3% of the employees work for the Unavailability of required jobs and 45% of the employees work for getting high pay package.

CHART 2: CHART SHOWING THE EMPLOYEES OPINION ON SUPERIOR - SUBORDINATE RELATIONSHIPS

INTERPRETATION :

From the above analysis, it can be inferred that 39% of the respondent think that the training programs helps in improving relationship among themselves, 35% of the respondent think that the training programs do not helps in improving relationship among themselves and 26% of the respondents are unsure that whether the training programs helps in improving relationship among themselves.

CHART 3 : CHART SHOWING COOPERATION OF DIFFERENT DEPARTMENTS.

INTERPRETATION

As per the analysis and the respondent’s view it’s observed that 42% of the respondent of different department cooperate with each other, 13% the respondent of different department do not cooperate with each other and 42% of the respondent say that they cooperate sometimes with each other.

CHART 4: CHART SHOWING THE ILL-EFFECTS OF NIGHT SHIFTS ON THE EMPLOYEES

INTERPRETATION

According to the research, it can be interpreted that 14.66% of the respondent believes that poor dietary intake is one of the ill-effect of night shift on the employees, 4.7% of the respondent believes that fatigue is another ill-effect of night shift on the employees, 28% takes sleep-disorder, 20.667% believes smoking and 32% of the respondents believes that stress are other ill-effect of night shifts on the employees

CHART 5: CHART SHOWING EMPLOYEEES OPINION ON ORGANISATION’S PAY IN RELATION WITH THE WORK PERFORMANCE.

INTERPRETATION

From the above analysis it can be concluded that 6% of the respondent strongly agree that their organization pay them salary by considering responsibilities at work, 61% of the respondent agree that their organization pay them salary by considering responsibilities at work, 29% of the respondent disagree and 2% of the respondent strongly disagree that their organization pay them salary by considering responsibilities at work.

CHART 6: CHART SHOWING EMPLOYEES OPINION ON THEIR SATISFACTION LEVELS :

INTERPRETATION

From the above analysis it can be interpreted that 20% of the respondent strongly agree towards the satisfaction provided towards the working condition, 75% of the respondent agree towards the satisfaction provided towards the working condition

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS :

1. Employees were also found complaining about poor dietary intake Majority ~ 68%, of population complained about health problems like stress, followed by (22%), increasing habit of smoking (31%), highly correlated to gender.
2. 32% of female and 68% of male are everyday

facing the challenge of the work life balance. Female are found to suffer more than males in terms to maintaining balance between their work and family

3. 57% of population said that they joined the industry because of high-pay package, 41% of the population say that they joined the industry for reputation, to pursue further education has been the reason for 26% people to join
4. The 42% of the employees are found agreeing in having cooperation with the employees from other departments
5. With regard to the shift schedule of work it's found that night shifts want to quit their job in next 1-2 years rather than those who work in day shifts.
6. According to the study 75% of the population agrees that they are satisfied with the working conditions provided by the company and 25% of them strongly agree that they are satisfied with the working environment provided by the company.

SUGGESTIONS:

1. Even though the BPO sector provides support to so many other sectors and so many other Industries, the society still isn't accepting the industry with all its glory.
2. Health risk assessments both pre-employment and periodic for employees should be conducted.
3. Full time counselors are needed to strike a balance between physical and mental rhythm to synchronize body clock.
4. Adequate salary should be paid to the employees in relation to the work they perform in the organization. There should be positive correlation between the rewards system and the job performance.
5. A grievances cell should be established so that employees are free to offer their comments and suggestions.

CONCLUSION :

1. In India there is a starting point in that organizations have recognized the need for and value of Work-Life Balance policies. But the debate has to now move into implementation and the Government could

play a critical role in being a catalyst of change.

2. An advantage that Indian industry will however have is learning from the experiences of other countries in what has worked and what has not. But as discussed earlier, there's no 'one size that fits all' and Indian companies will have to adapt policies to fit in with not just the nature of industry, profile of workforce and other such factors but also with the local culture and environment.
3. This study has been limited in that it has been done with a fairly restricted sample size. There are some areas however that are not supported by too much research like the impact of Work-Life Balance policies on senior managers which would be an interesting area for further exploration.

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Utilization of Management principles to find the GAPS in performance of Services

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Introduction :

Gap analysis generally refers to the activity of studying the differences between standards and the delivery of those standards (Rother, M., Shook, J., 2003). For example, it would be useful for a firm to document differences between customer expectation and actual customer experiences in the delivery of medical care. The differences could be used to explain satisfaction and to document areas in need of improvement.

However, in the process of identifying the gap, a before-and-after analysis must occur. This can take several forms. For example, in lean management we perform a Value Stream Map of the current process (Rother, M., Shook, J., 2003). Then we create a Value Stream Map of the desired state. The differences between the two define the "gap". Once the gap is defined, a game plan can be developed that will move the organization from its current state toward its desired future state.

What is exactly the GAPS

Technique for determining the steps to be taken in moving from a current state to a desired future-state. It begins with (1) listing of characteristic factors (such as attributes, competencies, performance levels) of the present situation ("what is"), (2) cross-lists factors required to achieve the future objectives ("what should be"), and then (3) highlights the 'gaps' that exist and need to be 'filled.' Also called need-gap analysis, needs analysis, and needs assessment (Frost, Julie. (1988)).

The GAPS in Educational and Financial service sectors

Due to GAP the service quality becomes affected for both the sectors under our discussion in this paper. The most common Gaps are identified and illustrated below.

From a service quality perspective, these include: (1) Service Quality Gap; (2) Management Understanding Gap; (3) Service Design Gap; (4) Service Delivery Gap; and (5) Communication Gap (Chakrapani, Chuck. (1988)).

Service Quality Gap - Indicates the difference between the service expected by customers and the service they actually receive. For example, customers may expect to wait only 20 minutes to see their result in University but, in fact, have to wait more than 20 hours. Or a customer has to wait to deposit their money in Bank account or insurance premium for a long time in queue (Parasuraman, Valerie Z., and Leonard L. Berry. (1988)).

Management Understanding Gap.

Represents the difference between the quality level expected by customers and the perception of those expectations by management. For example, in University, students as customer need to get thorough lecture of their course in classroom, not to complete syllabus promptly in schedule time. Second case is occurring in all most all the educational institutes, which requires further study.

Service Design Gap.

This is the gap between management's perception of customer expectations and the development of this perception into delivery standards (Schonberger, R.J., 1982). For example, management might perceive that customers expect someone to answer their telephone calls in a timely fashion. To customers, "timely fashion" may mean within thirty seconds.

Service Delivery Gap.

Represents the gap between the established delivery standards and actual service delivered. Given the above example, management may establish a standard such that telephone calls should be answered within thirty seconds.

Communication Gap.

This is the gap between what is communicated to consumers and what is actually delivered. For example, the technical institutes always emphasizes on the their placement strength, but actually after completion of the course students will get the scope not as per the propaganda. On the other hand, financial organization always

makes advertisement the profitability of their products, and customers will rush to purchase it, but at the end it is found profitability is not sufficient.

Implementing Gap Analysis

Gap analysis involves internal and external analysis. Externally, the firm must communicate with customers. Internally, it must determine service delivery and service design. Continuing with the service quality example, the steps involved in the implementation of gap analysis are:

1. Identification of customer expectations
2. Identification of customer experiences
3. Identification of management perceptions
4. Evaluation of service standards
5. Evaluation of customer communications

The identification of customer expectations and experiences might begin with focus-group interviews. Groups of customers, typically numbering as per admissible, are invited to discuss their satisfaction with services or products.

After focus-group interviews are completed, expectations and experiences are measured with more formal, quantitative methods. Expectations could be measured statistically using questionnaires with Likert scaling (Liker, J.K., 2004). Experience or perceptions about each of these attributes would be measured in a similar manner.

Gaps can be simply calculated after quantification the two measurements for each of the attributes. Management perceptions are measured much in the same manner. Groups of managers are asked to discuss their perceptions of customer expectations and experiences. A team can then be assigned the duty of evaluating manager perceptions, service standards, and communications to pinpoint discrepancies. After gaps are identified, management must take appropriate steps to fill or narrow the gaps.

The Importance of Service Quality Gap Analysis
- The main reason gap analysis is important to firms is the fact that gaps between customer expectations and customer experiences lead to customer dissatisfaction. Consequently,

measuring gaps is the first step in enhancing customer satisfaction. Additionally, competitive advantages can be achieved by exceeding customer expectations. Gap analysis is the technique utilized to determine where firms exceed or fall below customer expectations (Fuller, Neil.(1988)).

Product Applications - It should be noted that gap analysis is applicable to any aspect of industry where performance improvements are desired, not just in customer service (Womack, J.P., Jones, D.T., Roos, D., 1990). For example, the product quality gap could be measured by (and is defined as) the difference between the quality level of products expected by customers and the actual quality level. The measurement of the product quality gap is attained in the same manner as above.

Why Lean Management is required ? - On the above brief discussion we found that all the previous measures are very much interested to find out the defects of the system. But, it is more important to find out the wastage of the system (Womack, J.P., Jones, D.T., Roos, D., 1996). Wastage has no value addition. Lean Management methodology helps us to free the waste of the system.

On a example we can say, in University the Computer Science students attend workshop in the first year of their study. Mechanical workshop methodologies and techniques, which they learn, have no usage in their career. This is the waste.

On the other hand, in the Bank there are so many fixed deposit schemes. So, one who are purchasing a scheme having present rate of interest. When he will withdraw the cash after ten years same interest will be counted, but the market value will rise more and more in ten years. So, the person who is going to earn the interest after 10 years may be wastage.

Lean Management emphasizes on the wastage of product and services as per the present day needs and try to improve accordingly the system for the future day needs (Plenert, Gerhard. , (2001)).

Lean Philosophy

“Pursuing perfection to meet or exceed internal and external customer requirements by focusing on the entire value stream and a dedication to

continuous improvement, learning, and waste reduction (Liker, J.K., 1998, Womack, J.P., Jones, D.T., Roos, D., 1990).”

Some themes can be emphasized to minimize Gap

Theme	Description
"Emphasize participation and empowerment"	By creating a sense of ownership among as many stakeholders as possible, employees will be more likely to enthusiastically participate and internalize the suggested changes. "Leaders need to encourage members to take ownership and be autonomous independent thinkers".
"Create a change culture"	"Use culture as a tool or anchor to enable Change to occur". Encouraging thoughtful preparation and dissemination of ideas will help.
"Emphasize purpose and vision"	"Leaders should provide a consistent and strong justification for implementing the change".
"Emphasize communication"	"Communicating is key to working through problems and successfully implementing change". It should be open and honest, utilizing all means and vehicles of communication.

Conclusion:-

Educational sector and financial sector is the two pillar of Indian economical growth. A continual journey is occurring to free defects in these two sectors. In this paper we highlighted few common issues for both the sectors where some gaps are still prevailing. A discussion has also been taken in account to analysis the Gaps by statistical method. The most up-to-date management philosophy should be implemented to GAP analysis as it supports to free the wastage of the system rather to identify the defects and also gives the remedial measures.

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A Study on Retailers Attitude towards Processed Convenience Food In Coimbatore City

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ABSTRACT :

India is known as the 'land of retail outlets' due to the presence of largest number of retail outlets in the world, though most of these are small outlets. The food retail sector in India is largely unorganized mainly because it has not been given the status of an industry in the country. As a result, nobody perceived it to be an industry or a sector where large industrial corporate needed to enter or even explore. There are 12 million retail outlets in India of which 60% primarily sell food items. These are mostly neighborhood grocery stores. The traditional formats still dominate & account for 98% of retail. Though it is true the balance of market power is shifting to retailers, it is only to the extent that retailers know the demands of their customers. Consumer market power is becoming more embedded through the increased use of scanning data to decide product assortment, prices and marketing strategies. This Paper is focused on the retailer's aspects towards Processed Convenience food.

Key Words: Market Power, Marketing Strategies, Processed Convenience food

INTRODUCTION :

Retailing in South India - South India's retail food sector is undergoing a slow but steady transformation. Notable improvements have been made in the past three years. However, relative to the population size and increasing purchasing power within the middle and upper classes, growth in India's retail food sector has been slower than in most other Asian countries. In general, South India's retail food outlets are growing in both size and selection, offering more, packaged dry foods, some pre-packed fruits and vegetables, frozen foods and a variety of beauty, health and cleaning products. Stores range from small grocery stalls about 15 square feet in size offering around 300 products, to 4,000 foot supermarkets carrying thousands of products. Over 97 percent of the retail foods available in South Indian supermarkets are domestically manufactured. Regarding imported products, there is awareness at the dealer level.

Convenience Food in India – Retailing Perspectives The following could be considered as the factors that drives the industry on the positive growth path in India.

Income factor, Increasing awareness on health, Increasing quality consciousness, Need for convenience, Fast life style and Increasing consumer awareness due to media exposure

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the awareness of the selected branded processed convenience food items among the retailers.
2. To depict the retailers opinion on consumers attitude for preferring the branded processed convenience food.
3. To evaluate the level of satisfaction derived by the retailers while selling the branded processed convenience food.
4. To suggest on the basis of results of the study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

i) Research Design - The researcher aims at analyzing retailers attitude towards selected branded processed convenience food items marketed in Coimbatore city. Scientific enquiries aimed at discovering the relations & interactions among sociological, psychological and educational variable in a situation among selected groups attitudes, values, perceptions and behaviors.

ii) Area of the study - Growing income level and rapid change in house hold purchases and influence of processed convenience food culture among the middle and richer class house hold in Coimbatore city has motivated the researcher to select this region for the field research.

iii) Sample Size - As per 2001 census there are 2, 21,000 house hold in Coimbatore city. The population of the city is 9, 71,000 in urban area, which covers 88.29% of total population of 11 lakhs (1.1 million). The Coimbatore corporation council comprises of 72 wards and these wards are grouped into four zones of which 18 wards each in North, South, East and West zones.

The table shows the proportionate selection of consumers and retailers respondents as sample.

Sample Frame Work

Population density pattern	No of wards	Percentage %	No of wards	No of Retailers
Medium 10001 to 15000	16	32.65	3	150
High 15001 to 25000	18	36.73	4	200
Very High 25001 to 45000	10	20.41	2	100
Saturated Above 45001	5	10.21	1	50
Total	49	100	10	500

Source: - Computed from Coimbatore city corporation (Analysis)

From the total of 49 wards 10 per cent of wards are selected proportionately. Out of 10 wards 3 wards are selected from medium density pattern, 4 wards are selected from high, 2 wards are selected from very high and 1 ward from saturated. 50 retailers from each ward were selected for the study.

iv) Database and Methodology

The study being empirical in nature would require immense database and therefore, both primary as well as secondary data were collected.

v) Statistical Tools Applied

Descriptive analysis, Chi-square test, average rank analysis, average score analysis & anova.

SUGGESTIONS :

- The business profile of the surveyed retailer data reveals that 36 per cent of them has gained 5-10 years of experience in selling food items. 54 per cent of are seeking their business through grocery stores Retailers were dealing with these selected brands for a period of 3-4 years.
- In the process of analysis it is inferred that 56 per cent of the retailers opine that most of their customers visit twice a week to their store to procure processed convenience food items and majority of their customers repeatedly purchase Sakthi branded products.
- It is found from the study, majority of the retailers opined that their consumers prefer buying processed convenience food items as they 'lack knowledge on preparation of certain dishes'. Majority consider the convenience food as a better substitute for catering services.
- 60 per cent of the retailers felt that branded processed convenience food items as very good in terms of quality and product performances when compare to unbranded products. 84 per cent of the retailers stated that consumers are highly satisfied on Sakthi brand of convenience

food than others.

- It is inferred that 80 per cent of them believe that marketing of processed convenience food will enormously expand in future as they experience that convenience foods have highly impressed the customers and it sale trend absorbed to be increasing.
- Ease-to-Use is the primary statement given by retailer for sale of branded convenience food in their retail out lets. More over, 82 per cent of them have not received any complaint in marketing of convenience food products where as only 18 per cent had received the complaints against selected branded convenience food products, such as high price, lack of attractiveness in packages and non-availability of free samples.
- The factors influencing the consumer to buy processed convenience food items & opinion of the consumer to use convenience food as better substitution are two independent variables. It is also found that the promotional factors help to influence the customer to buy the processed convenience food items.

CONCLUSION :

Retailers operate in a harsh and fast changing environment, which offers threats as well as opportunities. Retailers are always searching for new marketing strategies to attract and hold customers. In past, retailers attracted consumers with unique products, more or better services than their competitors offered or credit cards. National brand manufacturers, in their drive for volume have placed their branded goods everywhere. This result in retail assortments is looking more and more alike. Service differentiation among retailers has also eroded. Customers have become smarter and more price sensitive hence service differences are shrinking. As a result many retailers are re-thinking their marketing strategies to withstand in the market.

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IFRS 13-Fair Value Measurement: An Understanding

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ABSTRACT: IFRS accounting is based on fair value measurement, in contrary to accounting in Indian GAAP where accounting is on historical cost basis. Several IFRS requires or permit to measure or disclose values of assets, liabilities or financial instruments on fair value. However due to limited guidance on fair value measurement in the individual Standards, IFRS 13 has been mandated for the financial year beginning on or after 1st January 2013 and it is to be applied prospectively. IFRS 13 defines fair value and replaces the requirement contained in individual standards.

Fair Value and IFRS

IFRS 13 applies when another IFRS requires or permits fair value measurements or disclosures about fair value measurements (and measurements, such as fair value less costs to sell, based on fair value or disclosures about those measurements), except as specified below:

1. The measurement and disclosure requirements of this IFRS do not apply to the following:
 - (a) share-based payment transactions (IFRS 2);
 - (b) leasing transactions (IAS 17); and
 - (c) measurements that have some similarities to fair value but are not fair value, such as NRV in IAS 2 Inventories or value in use in IAS 36 Impairment of Assets.
2. The disclosures required by this IFRS are not required for the following:
 - (a) plan assets measured at fair value in accordance with IAS 19 Employee Benefits;
 - (b) retirement benefit plan investments measured at fair value in accordance with IAS 26 Accounting and Reporting by Retirement Benefit Plans; and
 - (c) assets for which recoverable amount is fair value less costs of disposal in accordance with IAS 36

Fair value : Definition - IFRS-13 defines fair value as the price that would be received to sell an asset or paid to transfer a liability in an orderly

transaction between market participants at the measurement date (i.e. an exit price)

The definition of fair value emphasises that fair value is a market-based measurement, not an entity-specific measurement.

The IFRS explains that a fair value measurement requires an entity to determine the following:

- (a) the particular asset or liability being measured;
- (b) for a non-financial asset, the highest and best use of the asset and whether the asset is used in combination with other assets or on a stand-alone basis;
- (c) the market in which an orderly transaction would take place for the asset or liability; and
- (d) the appropriate valuation technique(s) to use when measuring fair value. The valuation technique(s) used should maximise the use of relevant observable inputs and minimise unobservable inputs.

Fair Value measurement: Asset or liability - A fair value measurement is for a particular asset or liability. Therefore, when measuring fair value an entity shall take into account the characteristics of the asset or liability if market participants would take those characteristics into account when pricing the asset or liability at the measurement date. Such characteristics include, for example, (a) the condition and location of the asset; and (b) restrictions, if any, on the sale or use of the asset.

Transaction under Fair Value measurement (Measured at the current market conditions).

A fair value measurement assumes that the transaction to sell the asset or transfer the liability takes place either:

- (a) in the principal market; or
- (b) in the absence of a principal market, in the most advantageous market.

If there is a principal market for the asset or

liability, the fair value measurement shall represent the price in that market even if the price in a different market is potentially more advantageous at the measurement date.

Fair Value is Market based measurement but can vary for different entities or their activities: Different entities may have different activities, therefore the principal market shall be considered from the perspective of the entity, thereby allowing for differences between and among entities with different activities. The entity must have access to the principal (or most advantageous) market at the measurement date. Because different entities with different activities may have access to different markets, the principal market for the same asset or liability might be different for different entities.

When there is no observable market to provide pricing information at the measurement date, a fair value measurement shall assume that a transaction takes place at that date, considered from the perspective of a market participant that holds the asset or owes the liability. That assumed transaction establishes a basis for estimating the price to sell the asset or to transfer the liability.

Market participants

An entity shall measure the fair value using the assumptions that market participants would use when pricing the asset or liability, assuming that market participants act in their economic best interest.

The price-Transaction costs, Transport cost

Fair value price is measured regardless of whether that price is directly observable or estimated using another valuation technique. The price in the principal (or most advantageous) market used to measure the fair value of the asset or liability shall not be adjusted for transaction costs. Transaction costs shall be accounted for in accordance with the respective IFRSs. Transaction costs are not a characteristic of an asset or a liability; rather, they are specific to a transaction and will differ depending on how an entity enters into a transaction for the asset or liability. Transaction costs do not include transport costs. If location is a characteristic of the asset (as might be the case,

for example, for a commodity), the price in the principal (or most advantageous) market shall be adjusted for the costs, if any, that would be incurred to transport the asset from its current location to that market.

Non-financial assets (Highest and best use for non-financial assets)

A fair value measurement of a non-financial asset takes into account a market participant's ability to generate economic benefits by using the asset in its highest and best use or by selling it to another market participant that would use the asset in its highest and best use. The highest and best use of a non-financial asset takes into account the use of the asset that is physically possible, legally permissible and financially feasible.

Application to liabilities and an entity's own equity instruments:

A fair value measurement assumes that a financial or non-financial liability or an entity's own equity instrument (i.e. equity interests issued as consideration in a business combination) is transferred to a market participant at the measurement date. The transfer of a liability or an entity's own equity instrument assumes the following:

(a) A liability would remain outstanding and the market participant transferee would be required to fulfil the obligation. The liability would not be settled with the counterparty or otherwise extinguished on the measurement date.

(b) An entity's own equity instrument would remain outstanding and the market participant transferee would take on the rights and responsibilities associated with the instrument. The instrument would not be cancelled or otherwise extinguished on the measurement date.

When a quoted price for the transfer of an identical or a similar liability or entity's own equity instrument is not available and the identical item is held by another party as an asset, an entity shall measure the fair value of the liability or equity instrument from the perspective of a market participant that holds the identical item as an asset at the measurement date.

When a quoted price for the transfer of an identical or a similar liability or entity's own equity instrument is not available and the identical item is not held by another party as an asset, an entity shall measure the fair value of the liability or equity instrument using a valuation technique from the perspective of a market participant that owes the liability or has issued the claim on equity.

Valuation techniques

An entity shall use valuation techniques that are appropriate in the circumstances and for which sufficient data are available to measure fair value, maximising the use of relevant observable inputs and minimising the use of unobservable inputs. IFRS 13 describes three valuation techniques to determine the fair value.

- a. The market approach
- b. The cost approach
- c. The income approach

Discount rate adjustment technique - The discount rate adjustment technique uses a single set of cash flows from the range of possible estimated amounts, whether contractual or promised (as is the case for a bond) or most likely cash flows. In all cases, those cash flows are conditional upon the occurrence of specified events (i.e. contractual or promised cash flows for a bond are conditional on the event of no default by the debtor). The discount rate used in the discount rate adjustment technique is derived from observed rates of return for comparable assets or liabilities that are traded in the market. Accordingly, the contractual, promised or most likely cash flows are discounted at an observed or estimated market rate for such conditional cash flows (i.e. a market rate of return).

The discount rate adjustment technique requires an analysis of market data for comparable assets or liabilities. Comparability is established by considering the nature of the cash flows (i.e. whether the cash flows are contractual or non-contractual and are likely to respond similarly to changes in economic conditions), as well as other

factors (i.e. credit standing, collateral, duration, restrictive covenants and liquidity). Alternatively, if a single comparable asset or liability does not fairly reflect the risk inherent in the cash flows of the asset or liability being measured, it may be possible to derive a discount rate using data for several comparable assets or liabilities in conjunction with the risk-free yield curve (i.e. using a 'build-up' approach).

Disclosure requirements - An entity shall disclose information that helps users of its financial statements assess both of the following:

- a. for assets and liabilities that are measured at fair value on a recurring or non-recurring basis in the statement of financial position after initial recognition, the valuation techniques and inputs used to develop those measurements.
- b. for recurring fair value measurements using significant unobservable inputs, the effect of the measurements on profit or loss or other comprehensive income for the period.

Conclusion :

Though IFRS 13 is applicable from 1st January 2013, yet most of the concept, principle and disclosure requirements exist in the current practices of fair value measurement through the respective standards. The Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA) of India has issued 35 Accounting Standards, in line with IFRS, named IND AS (though MCA has not declared the date of applicability) but IND AS has the mandate of Fair value measurement in the concerned standards.

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ROI of Training and Development Activities

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Introduction :

Return on Investment (ROI) is a financial metric that can be used to evaluate training and development investments. Return on investment (ROI) has become one of the most challenging and intriguing issues facing the human resources development (HRD) and performance improvement fields. Thus, this paper discusses overall impact of ROI of Training and Development activities in evaluation of these activities of the organisation.

Defining ROI - Return on Investment (ROI) in training and development (T&D) means measuring all the economic returns generated from an investment in a T&D programme. These returns are then compared with the true cost of the programme to determine an average annual rate of return of the investment. All capital assets need to earn a rate of return for the business to make a profit and stay in business; ROI is about judging the investment in T&D on similar criteria to other investment in the business.

Some returns can be easily measured, such as increase in sales after a sales training programme, but others such as employee satisfaction, turnover rate, and complaint levels require conversion to a monetary amount. Some costs can also be easily measured, such as hire of training rooms; however other costs need further analysis to determine, such as the cost of administration of the T&D department.

The intense focus on performance in public companies has made ROI increasingly important. The only way to guarantee that projects and programmes receive funding is to show how they boost the bottom line. An ROI evaluation fulfils senior management's requirements to justify training budgets and investments.

Need for the Study - In the last few decades, this approach has been applied to asset purchase decisions (computer systems, factory machines, or service vehicles, for example), "go-no-go" decisions for projects and programmes of all

kinds (including marketing, recruiting, and training programmes), and to more traditional investment decisions (such as the management of stock portfolios or the use of venture capital).

A study of 15 countries in the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development found that the majority of enterprises believe employee training is responsible for "productivity improvements, greater workforce flexibility, and savings on material and capital costs, improved quality of the final product or service, and a more motivated workforce."

Why Measure ROI of A Training Programme ?

Several issues are driving the increased interest in, and application of, the ROI process, the most common being:

- The pressure from clients and senior managers which show that the return on their training investment is probably the most influential drive
- The competitive economic pressures that are causing intense scrutiny of all expenditures
- The general trend towards accountability with all staff support groups that is causing some HRD departments to measure their contribution
- To justify the existence of the training department by showing how it contributes to the organization's objectives and goals
- To decide whether to continue or discontinue the training programmes.

Scope of the Study :

Although the interest in the topic has heightened and much progress has been made, it is

still an issue that challenges even the most sophisticated and progressive HRD departments and those involved with management development programs. Some professionals argue that it is not possible to calculate the ROI of many programs, while others develop measures and ROI calculations. Regardless of

the position taken on the issue, the reasons for measuring the return are still there (Phillips, 1977). Most professionals involved in training and development share a concern that they must eventually show a return on their training investment and thereby abandon some of the more traditional methods of evaluating programs.

Objectives of the Study :

- 1) To understand the concept of ROI of Training and Development Activities.
- 2) To overview the role of ROI in evaluation of Training and Development Activities.

Research Methodology :

This is purely secondary base paper, where we have used descriptive method in which data collection has done from various sources like reference books, internet, journals, and magazines and so on.

Limitations of the study:

The study is based on the secondary data where we cannot draw firm conclusions.

Review of Literature:

Many organizations around the globe are using cost saving approaches so that they can begin conducting ROI evaluation within their current budget while others are using such approaches in order to increase the number of ROI studies they conduct. General cost saving approaching for measuring programmes at the ROI level introduced by Phillips (1997a) have been proven to significantly decrease resource requirements while still providing sound, credible data. Despite these factors, establishing an evaluation culture is no easy task.

In many ways, implementing a system-wide ROI effort is similar to implementing a large-scale change initiative. The concept of ROI has been used for centuries. The 75th anniversary issue of Harvard Business Review (HBR) traced the tools used to measure the results in organizations. In the early issues of HBR, during the 1920s, ROI was the emerging tool to place a value on the payoff of investments.

In recent years, the application of the concept has been expanded to all types of investments including training and education, change initiatives, and technology (Phillips, 2000a).

With increased adoption and use, it appears that ROI is here to stay. Today, hundreds of organizations, representing manufacturing, service, non-profit, and government, are routinely using ROI calculations for education and training programmes. A professional society, The ROI Network™, with over 500 members, allows practitioners an opportunity to share information and tools around ROI. The networks have been formed within the organizations to focus on the ROI and accountability issue. Almost 1,000 individuals have been certified to implement the process in their organizations. Three casebooks have been developed to show specific applications of ROI (Phillips, 1994; 1997; 2000c). A fourth casebook describes successful implementation of the ROI process (Phillips, 1998). This level of interest and activity is evidence that the ROI process is here to stay. There are good reasons why return on investment is so significant. Although the viewpoints and explanations may vary, some things are very clear. First, in most organizations, education and training budgets have continued to grow year after year. As expenditures grow, accountability becomes a more critical issue. A growing budget creates a larger target for internal critics, often prompting the development of an ROI process.

Second, Total Quality Management and Continuous Process Improvement have drawn increased attention to measurement issues.

Today, organizations measure processes and outputs that were not previously measured, monitored, and reported. This measurement focus has placed increased pressure on the education and training function to develop measures of programme success. A paper (Buckberry, 2004) has been developed to provide to members of Computer Education and Management Association (CEdMA) some basic introductory information and ideas to assist in the preparation of their own customized ROI processes. CEdMA's clients are typically purchasers of IT software and hardware, and CEdMA members are responsible for the provision of training to these clients. The question this paper addresses is, "How do we help customers understand and justify for themselves

the need to invest properly and comprehensively in training, and how do we present the comparative benefits of different approaches to training?” Implementing some form of measurement process is as important for managing training programmes and investment, as it is for any other project requiring significant financial investment by a business. Training programmes consume resources (i.e., they take people’s time and money), but they are also critical to maximizing the return on investment in other programmes or products (e.g., the effective introduction of software systems requires users to be able to use the systems effectively if the potential benefit of the software systems is to be realized in practice), as well as generally improving the productivity of the workforce. If ROI is to be successfully managed and measured, it is important that the process be included early in the planning cycle for the training programmes. (Buckberry, 2004).

Philips and Philips (2009) describe the ROI methodology, a measurement process that was developed almost 30 years ago and refined over the years to the point that it is now becoming a staple for many HR functions. During difficult times in the economy, nothing is more important to top executives than knowing the true value of a particular project or programme. “Show me the money” has become a battle cry for many executives demanding that any new HR project or programme shows its value even before it is implemented and, certainly, the impact and return on investment (ROI) after it has been implemented. Around the globe, HR executives are taking a look at the ROI process as a way to show credible values, including financial ROI. This article describes why and how ROI is used to show the contribution of HR programmes and improve them further so that they can add more value, build support for HR, enhance commitments, and concretize important business relationships. This method can be used to show the value of major programmes and projects and establish HR as a business partner. With the ROI process, the HR staff and the client would know the specific contribution of an HR Programme.

Evaluation Levels

Evaluation Level	Description	Characteristics
Level 1 “Did they like it?”	Measuring Reaction and Identifying Planned Actions	Measures participants’ reaction to the program, and outlines specific plans for implementation of learning to the job.
Level 2 “Did they learn?”	Measuring Cognitive Learning and Retention	Measures skills, knowledge, or attitude changes as a result of the training.
Level 3 “Do they use it?”	Assessing Application of the program training on the job	Measures actual changes in behaviour on the job, and specific applications of the training material.
Level 4 “Did it impact the bottom line?”	Identifying business results from the training	Measures the business impact of the training (e.g. measures changes in output, quality, costs, time, productivity or other business metrics)
Level 5 “What is the return on learning investment?”	Calculating Return on Investment	Compares the monetary value of the results with the costs for the program.

In most organisations, measuring training effectiveness at all Levels 1-4 is not feasible for all participants and for all projects. In practice, the organisation must set targets for the scope of evaluations at each level, and for the critical training courses or programmes which have most importance to the success of the organisation. Typical targets for measurement activities at each level are:

- Level 1: 100% of participants/courses provide effectiveness data
- Level 2: 50-70% of participants/courses provide effectiveness data
- Level 3: 30-50% of participants/courses provide effectiveness data
- Level 4: 10-20% of participants/courses provide effectiveness data
- Level 5: 5-10% of actual ROI is measured, and extrapolated to the overall program.

From this, we can see that most organisations will initially only fully calculate ROI in detail on a sample of the courses and participants. It is therefore essential to identify those courses and participants who are:

- Representative of the overall population
- Taking part in important or high impact programs
- Able to accurately assess the impact of training on their jobs
- Amenable to providing the full depth of data required

ROI Formula - The formula for evaluating Training investments is net programme benefits divided by cost.

$$\text{Evaluating Training Investment} = \frac{\text{Program Benefits}}{\text{Program Cost}}$$

The ratio is usually expressed as percentage When the fractional values are multiplied by 100.

ROI can thus be expressed as :

$$\text{ROI (\%)} = \frac{\text{Net Programme Benefits}}{\text{Programme Costs}} \times 100$$

Calculating ROI requires that business results data must be converted to monetary benefits. It is important to be able to allocate financial value to results such as

- Improved productivity
- Time saved
- Output increased
- Enhanced quality
- Reduced employee turnover
- Decreased absenteeism
- Improved customer satisfaction

Conclusion :

By understanding this basic conceptual phenomenon one can easily go for successful implementation of ROI evaluation. So, one need to understand that it is not a backward-looking audit of training but a tool to ensure that future training is targeted and it should be effective. It is not principally about cost saving but about objective evaluation and re-engineering of Training and Development programmes to meet the needs of the 21st Century global economy.

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CORPORATE VALUES AND SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES: SOCIAL WORK PERSPECTIVE

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CSR : CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY:

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a relatively new concept of which there is no exact or universally accepted definition. The concept revolves around the notion that organizations are "obliged" to take responsibility for their activities that have an impact not only on their employees and customers, but also on the environment and affected communities as a whole. In other words, these organizations must look at the interests of society.

EU Commission: CSR is essentially a concept whereby companies decide voluntarily to contribute to a better society and a cleaner environment. It is also called cooperate conscience, sustainable responsibility. It is a built in & self regulating mechanism, & a process with the aim to encourage the impact of any activity on the environment, consumers, employees, communities & other members of public sphere.

The term Corporate Social Responsibility came into common use in the late 1960s & early 1970s. ISO 26000-Social Responsibility is the recognized international standard for CSR. It aimed at both public and private organization. It informed the organization how to perform in socially responsible way. UN has developed the principals for responsible investments.

CSR can no longer be seen as a "cheque book philanthropy," according to Jackie Gray in her article on social responsibility for National Business Initiative. She mentions how the mere concept of CSR envisages an obligation of corporate companies to aid society and the environment and that due to much criticism over the motives of these companies, there is now a dire need for accountability and lucidity in all spheres. She also discusses pressures that companies face now from customers, NGOs,

investors and the government to invest in "causes," which almost create a tacit obligation on them to act accordingly.

CSR IN INDIA:

In INDIA no body is clear about the CSR the INDIAN Government has been trying to make it mandatory for companies to spend 2% of net profit on CSR. It is a blurred picture. Some companies are providing lunch for CSR & some define CSR by tackling the Global Warming & Environmental issues.

INDIA is the country where corporate philanthropy in vogue, corporate philanthropy & CSR both are different but people always intermingle CSR & Philanthropy. In INDIA 100% overlap is seen in CSR & Philanthropy. Recently there are some initiatives which are taken by the government as to provide the vocational training to the people, how ever it is difficult to practice but a way to create the conscientisation regarding the CSR.

From my point of view CSR is essential, but people have to decide on their own, how to contribute to society, how to make profit for long term, not in monetary terms but also in terms of ethics, values & morals. It is important to make profit but on the cost of the future generation & their needs. Present is important but future also have some importance so conscientisation regarding CSR is more crucial aspect. This should not be imposed on the corporate world but it should be imposed on every person, every group & on every section of the society.

INDIA'S philanthropic community is also against the compulsory CSR. Many people quote that if you make things mandatory, people will find the means & ways to get out of it.

According to CII (Confederation of Indian Industry) compulsory corporate responsibility would be counter productive. The FICCI

(Federation of Indian Chamber Of Commerce & Industry) suggested tax breaks for those who meet the voluntary targets. CSR is the part of new companies' bill. The Companies Act of 1956 has several clauses regarding CSR. It is revised in 2009. It contains many provisions which are important to industries.

INITIATIVE TAKEN BY THE GOVERNMENT:

First international summit was held in 2008 in New Delhi. CSR is comprehended differently by different people report titled CSR: TOWARDS A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE – quoted by the idea of philanthropy & business efforts are limited to one time financial grants.

2009 - First Govt. paper on CSR release by the ministry of corporate affairs. Also talks of health, Culture, Social welfare & education. 2009 – Former minister of corporate affairs Khurshid released the 2009 guideline – Corporate growth widening the gap between India & Bharat. & this gap needs to be bridged. 2011 – India Philanthropy Report 2011 by Arpan Shah – It is like a Venn diagram, where there is an overlap between the two.

INITIATIVE TAKEN BY THE COOPRATIVES

- Boosting profits Gujarat Ambuja, one of the country's leading cement manufacturers, reports that 'our efforts to achieve world standards in environment protection have had the happy outcome of substantially improving efficiency and profitability'.
- Cutting costs Reliance Industries' energy conservation measures have saved the company 1150 million rupees per annum.
- Increasing revenues HLL's Project Shakti creates income-generating opportunities for the under-privileged rural women, while giving the company an enhanced access to hitherto unexplored rural areas.
- Strengthening brand value In February 2004, Infosys was among seven international companies to be chosen in the first annual list of 'Top Brands with a Conscience'.
- Enhancing reputation The Oil and Natural

Gas Corporation has found that its community development programme has 'generated tremendous goodwill and earned the company the reputation of being a company that cares'.

- Improving morale Tata Steel believes that helping the community also provides a new perspective to its employees, thereby strengthening employee morale.
- The Coca-Cola company has teamed with the World Wildlife Fund to protect the arctic habitat by releasing 1.4 billion redesigned white Coke cans each showing a polar bear, which the company hopes will raise awareness of this cause. Coke made an initial donation of \$2 million to the World Wildlife Fund, and Coke will match up to \$1 million that Coke drinkers will be able to donate to the campaign (Business Briefing, 2011).
- McDonald's is so extensively involved in charitable activities and civic affairs in local communities throughout the United States that it produces through its corporate charitable division, Ronald McDonald House Charities of South Florida, special multi-page advertising supplements to local newspapers to describe the company's many socially responsible activities – from grants, "Wish Lists," scholarships, volunteer work to, of course, the Ronald McDonald House itself (Ronald McDonald House Charities of South Florida, 2012).

BARRIERS OF CSR :

- Absence of clear linkage between CSR and financial success
- Low voluntary adoption of CSR- Leads to 'green washing'
- Lack of mechanisms to measure, monitor evaluate and report impacts
- Two myths- Smaller companies think it the responsibility of the bigger ones and It is mainly philanthropic exercise
- High 'overheads' of implementing and sustaining CSR efforts.
- No universally accepted frameworks.

CONCLUSION :

In India CSR is seen as in the form of charity and the philanthropy. Culture, religion, family, values and tradition and industrialisation had an influence on CSR. After independence there is an increase of responsibility on industrialists to show more consciousness towards the society. The time period of 1960-1980 was the time of mixed economy, the emergence of PSUs was taken place during this time.

1980 to till now companies abandoned their traditional engagement with CSR and integrated the sustainable approach in business.

Today this is not a new concept. Many companies adopted the sustainable approach as the TATA Group, Aditya Birla Group, and Indian Oil Corporation.

Numbers of people now feel that it is an essential part of the corporate policy and it will help you out in creating goodwill that creates the better society than ever. Recent trends have shown strong bonding between the Companies and the N.G.O. The social work and social worker helps in bridging the gap between the traditional role and new concept to create the shared values which is common in both the area social work and in corporate sector.

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Politically Incorrect Narrative in Githa Hariharan's In Times of Siege

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Whether it was the scraping of AK Ramanujan's essay – 'Three Hundred Ramayanas: Five Examples and Three Thoughts on Translation' from Delhi University syllabus of BA (Hons.) History or Rohinton Mistry's novel 'Such A Long Journey' got dropped from Mumbai University's BA English Literature Course on the protest of Shiv Sena scion Aditya Thackarey by the then Vice Chancellor Rajan Welunkar, these and many other incidences of such nature by political, bureaucratic or academic echelons reflect of a malady that our society suffers, that either be political correct or ready to face the backlash of murkiest kind. In a liberal democracy like India where pluralism and multiculturalism are the hallmarks of progressive and inclusive society, succumbing to this kind of blatant hooliganism suggests of the fact that, at least, the academics holding the highest places should not give up for the sake of clinging to power and should take a clear stand to vindicate the ways of liberal democracy.

Githa Hariharan in her novel *In Times of Siege* (2003) chillingly portrays the aftermath of similar kind of incidence occurring in the life of an ordinary history professor of an open university. Parallels between the two incidences cited above and the narrative of the novel are too obvious and make one feel whether Hariharan could intuitively feel the air in the atmosphere and predict the resemblance so realistically. *In Times of Siege* covers the span of two months (late August - October, 2000) in the life of Shiv Murthy, a fifty-two year old professor of history at Kasturba Gandhi Central University. The comfortable tedium of his existence is rudely broken by a controversy over a lesson that has been in use for some years. This module for the history paper of medieval India has been prepared by Shiv Murthy in which he describes the political and social attainments of twelfth century poet-reformer Basava or Basavanna. The louts of the Itihas Suraksha Manch have belatedly discovered that the saintly Basava has been depicted as human. The Manch has three demands – first, an apology by the professor, second, retract of the lesson and third, a more outrageous one, the rewritten lesson should be submitted first to Manch before sending to printing press. As according to Shiv Murthy, the lesson does not

distort history by any stretch of imagination, he refuses to apologize. Events escalate: the militant fundos make a lot of fuss, the media takes an interest, people inside and outside academia choose sides. For example, one of the faculty member Arya, with strong right wing inclination, is all for Murthy's blood and takes head-on other faculty members whom he considers leftist – "But again, it is Arya who speaks up before the head. 'The Manch represents public sentiment. History and everything else should respect this. For years leftists and pseudo-secular historians have been filling committees with their agents. Now their monopoly is over and they are making a hue and cry.'" (P-125,126) Hariharan nicely allows the dispute to unfold, without focusing too narrowly on it: this is a novel about politics and political correctness and academia (and it's clear on which side she stands), but her focus on Murthy, who often remains a bit on the periphery of events, and his day to day life prevents the book from bogging down in petty politics alone.

There is also an intriguing development in Shiv Murthy's life with arrival of young university girl Meena to his house who has fractured her leg and is daughter of Murthy's friend. In fact, both the narratives – political and personal – run concurrently in the novel. Murthy has an uneventful life with a working wife Rekha and a young daughter who has recently landed up a job in US. When novel opens, Murthy's wife and daughter are in the US and he being local guardian to Meena has gone to her hostel to bring her to his house. When the controversy about the lesson breaks out, the divisions on the ideological lines are clear and loud. Meena, her friend Amar, Manzar etc along with some faculty members toes the progressive line where facts of history are to be looked and interpreted with objectivity, and persons like Arya and who belong to Itihas Surksha Manch believe that glorification of Hindu religion and mythology has to be reinforced over the various curricula in India which according to them is too leftist in nature to be replaced by a kind of Hindu chauvinism. And of course, there are host of others who are fence-sitters and they negotiate their position with convenience. When these battle lines are drawn, its clear that Githa Hariharan belongs to which

side.

Along with this over-current of politics being played with the context of curriculum design, there is a deeply personal and existential slant to the narrative in the form of Murthy's father, a freedom fighter, who disappeared as a disillusioned, disheartened person on seeing the condition of India after independence. Parallels between Basava and Murthy's are drawn in very obvious manner by the author, perhaps this is to explain Murthy's besieged existence. Hariharan writes –

“Shiv tries to understand this river. Basava's powerful river. It is a river that never stands still. It keeps moving, this river, flowing day after day, night after night. What can a river do but flow? From a distance, it is just a simple body of water, mindlessly acting out of its nature, its constant movement a quest without a purpose. But close up, all complacent assumptions of simplicity vanish. There is nothing obvious about this river. Nothing about this river is what it seems. Close up, the river is actually two rivers. Two rivers flowing down their separate courses, then meeting, parting, meeting, parting, till they come to a point of union, a union deep enough for them to emerge flowing as a composite third river.” (P-106, 107.)

In an interview to Luan Gaines Githa Hariharan explains how the three strands – emotional, political and existentialism – explains the persona of Shiv Murthy – “It's not so much a romance as plain lust on his part growing into something more difficult to name. And perhaps it's this sort of undefined, unconsummated relationship that can finally be the most powerful impulse to change. As far as his memory of his dead father, and his knowledge of the medieval poet are concerned – they (along with Meena) – challenge him to aspire to their rather high standards of courage. And Shiv, like most “heroes” of our times, is a reluctant one. His act of courage, finally, is simply not to give in, to continue to teach, to read and write as he thinks right despite government or mob censorship. It sounds mock-heroic almost, but from our own experience, we know it's not all that easy to do.”¹

In these difficult times when political correctness is the only discourse happening in the society and major's hegemony is celebrated in one way or the other, Hariharan's novel comes as a huge warning, not only to society at

large but also to creative artists, intellectuals, academics and cultural activists that we need to be critically aware of our times and should shed-off the reticence of being complacent fence-sitters. In the above quoted interview, Hariharan further tries to emphasize that we need not only to accept one's otherness but we should try to celebrate it -

Que. As you say, the world we live in has become black and white, with no room for differences. What actions can alter this paradigm and/or temper the increasing extremism? Is a rational discussion even possible?

Ans. Whether it seems possible or not, what other sane options do we have? Even if it were desirable – and I can't see how it can be – the world is never going to be one tribe, one race, one nationality, just as it is never going to be either just men or just women. It seems to me that the important thing is to move from mere tolerance to active learning about others so we can actually celebrate differences. It certainly makes life more exciting, don't you think?²

As has been commented in Far Eastern Economic Review -In Times of Siege is a disturbing fictional portrait of the ideological polarization and sectarian conflict that in recent years have permeated every facet of life in India. Hariharan captures Shiv's besieged existence with just the right amount of angst, confusion, polemic and humour. She has written a persuasive book that tells of the perils of sectarianism and silence in the face of oppression.

Thus Shiv Murthy's realization of the self through this tumult of happening is the culmination of this narrative that teaches us to take a stand in the midst of a crisis. “Now the stick is superfluous. This is what Meena and her unlikely allies in contingency, his father, Basava, and the thought policing touts of Itihas Surksha Manchhave forced Shiv to see. Once he throws away all safe crutches, he can truly walk in the present. Be free to be curious, to speculate; to debate, dissent. Reaffirm the value of the only heirloom he needs from the past, the right to know a thing in all the ways possible.” (P-194)

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Prospects and Trends in Turmeric Trade

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Abstract :

Turmeric is one of the major species in India. India contributes to 80% of world turmeric production and is the largest exporter of turmeric. The major importing countries of turmeric are Japan, Sri Lanka, Iran, United Arab Emirates, United States, United Kingdom and Ethiopia. Turmeric is used in culinary, cosmetics, ayurvedic preparation, and pharma and dying. It is closely associated with everything auspicious – hence indispensable element in all festivals and celebrations. Turmeric is exported as dry turmeric, turmeric powder and oleoresin and other value added products. This paper deals with international trade and worldwide market trends pertaining to turmeric (*curcuma longa*).

Keywords: Turmeric, Production, Processing, Value added Products

Introduction :

India is a land that abounds in variety and diversity - Variety in its spice and diverse in its blend and culinary preparation. The heritage of India's multicolored palette is really an indication of spice. Since ancient times India has been and continues to be the treasure trove for spice lovers and spice merchants. Inquire the ancient mariners where to find spice and they'd come sailing towards the Indian seas. Turmeric, pepper, cinnamon, saffron, cardamom, chilly, nutmeg, cloves, cumin, etc. The trails of spices are endless as the desire to satisfy one's appetite. The global demand for spices and business opportunities for spice traders and manufacturers have grown up in the recent years.

Even without the king pepper and queen cardamom there may be Indian dishes but definitely not without turmeric, the golden spice. Without turmeric every Indian kitchen is bare and incomplete. Turmeric is considered sacred in every Indian household plays a vital role in Indian rituals and ceremonies. Turmeric is not only used for domestic culinary purposes, it also plays an important role in medicine and in the manufacture of dyeing agents.

Turmeric Global Scenario - India is the largest producer, consumer and exporter turmeric in the world. Other producers of turmeric include Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Taiwan, China, Burma (Myanmar), and Indonesia. Apart from the Asian countries, Turmeric is also produced in the Caribbean and Latin America: Costa Rica, Jamaica, Haiti, Peru, and Brazil. The major importing countries are the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Japan, Iran, Bangladesh, Singapore, Netherlands, and Sri Lanka accounting for nearly 80% of turmeric traded the world over. Global production of turmeric is round 6 to 7 lakh tons.

Turmeric Production in India

In India, Turmeric is cultivated in Andhra Pradesh, Tamilnadu, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Kerala, Orissa, West Bengal and North Eastern states.

Table No: 1. Turmeric - Area and Production

State	Area	Share	Production	Share
Andhra Pradesh	57.7	38.4	280.7	53.8
Tamil Nadu	16.7	11.1	65.9	12.6
Orissa	23.7	15.8	56.2	10.8
West Bengal	12.2	8.1	22.9	4.4
Karnataka	6.0	4.0	27.5	5.3
Gujarat	0.9	0.6	13.0	2.5
Kerala	2.9	2.0	6.3	1.2
Maharashtra	7.0	4.7	6.0	1.1
North East*	16.0	10.6	26.6	5.1
All India	150.3	100.0	522.1	100.0

In India, turmeric is traded at Nizamabad, Dugirala in Andhra Pradesh, Sangli in Maharashtra, Salem, Erode, Dharmapuri and Coimbatore in Tamilnadu. Also, turmeric is traded in Indian commodity exchanges namely, National Commodity & Derivatives Exchange Ltd. and The Spices and Oilseeds Exchange Ltd.

Turmeric Varieties

Some of the popular varieties of turmeric are Erode, Salem, Duggirala, Rajpuri, Alleppey, Tekkurpet, Sugandham, Amalapuram (from Andhra Pradesh), Moovattupuzha,

Wynadu (from Kerala) and Lakaday (Meghalaya), etc.

Post Harvest Processing

Chart 2. Post Harvest Processing

Curing - Fingers are separated from mother rhizomes. The fresh turmeric is cured for obtaining dry turmeric. Curing involves boiling the rhizomes until soft. It is performed to gelatinize the starch for a more uniform drying, and to remove the fresh earthy odor. Due to this process, the coloring material is diffused uniformly through the rhizome.

Drying - The cooked fingers are dried in the sun by spreading in 5-7 cm thick layers on bamboo mats or drying floor. A thinner layer is not desirable as the colour of the dried product may be adversely affected. It may take 10-15 days for the rhizomes to become completely dry. Artificial drying using cross flow hot air at a maximum temperature of

600° C is also found to give a satisfactory product.

Polishing - Dried turmeric has a poor appearance and rough dull colour outside the surface with scales and root bits. The appearance is improved by smoothening and polishing the outer surface by manual or mechanical rubbing. In order to impart attractive yellow colour, turmeric suspension in water is added to the polishing drum in the last 10 minutes.

Grading, packing and storage - Bulk rhizomes are graded into fingers, bulbs and splits. The Indian Standards for turmeric follow the Agmark specifications (Agricultural Directorate of Marketing), to insure quality and purity. Well-cured and dried turmeric is generally packed in new gunny bags which

Value Added Products

Turmeric powder - Ground turmeric is mostly used on the retail market, and by the food processors. Rhizomes are ground to approximately 60-80 mesh particle size. In the food industry, it is mostly used to color and flavor mustard. It is also used in chicken bouillon and soups, sauces, gravies, and dry seasonings. Recently the powder has also been used as a colorant in cereals.

Curry powder - Turmeric is such an important ingredient in curry powder that it merits special mention. In its export statistics of spices, the Indian Spice Board specifically lists curry powder exports. The turmeric content in curry powder blends ranges from 10-15% to 30%. Curry mixes for vegetarian dishes contain less turmeric, in the range of 5 to 10%, because of the bitter flavor it would impart to the dish.

Oleoresins - Turmeric extractives, or oleoresins, are obtained by solvent extraction of the powdered or comminuted rhizome. This process yields about 12 % of an orange/red viscous liquid, which, depending on the solvent used for extraction and on the turmeric type and cultivar, contains various proportions of the coloring matter, i.e. the curcuminoids, the volatile oils which impart the flavor to the product, and non-volatile fatty and resinous materials.

Essential oil - Turmeric essential oil has less

commercial value, as opposed to oleoresin. However, there is an increasing literature showing medicinal activities of turmeric, of which some are attributable to compounds present in the volatile fraction. Turmeric essential oil is obtained by distillation, or by supercritical fluid extraction of the powdered rhizome. It is also the product of curcuminoids purification from oleoresins.

Conclusion :

India being the dominant player in turmeric trade which has got good international demand. Indian turmeric and farmers and traders have to tune up to the international expectations and standards. Future of turmeric trade seems to be very bright due to varied use of turmeric throughout the globe. With more involvement of traders and farmers along with the assistance of the Government on technological and infrastructural front will make turmeric trade in India fetching more value and volume.

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A STUDY ON ADVERTISING EFFECT AND ITS IMPACT ON REAL ESTATE

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INDIAN REAL ESTATE-AN OVERVIEW

The booming real estate, property in India has become a dream for every potential investor . All are eyeing Indian property market for a wide variety of reasons are as follows:

1. The advertisement is to create a favorable climate for improving investment by providing crystal clear information about real estate
2. Indian real estate sector is on boom and this is the right time to invest in property in India to reap the highest rewards.
3. Increase in population level.
4. The available resources with the young generation.
5. The liberalization policies usages in Indian government.
6. The nuclear family life style.

According to the National Association of Realtors, almost 75 percent of the people use the Internet to find their new home. Modern communication technologies offer an optimal way to advertise real estate. But there are slightly more traditional methods that are considered to work well, ie real estate advertising on a local newspaper or on the local TV channels.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the customer attitude towards advertisements on real estate business.
2. To study the present factor for the growth of real estate.
3. To study the future constraints of real estate investment.
4. To offer suggestion based on studies.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Upto the end of 2012 real estate sector in Coimbatore was in high rate. There is a situation of boom in this sector. There were many channels for advertising real estate. But in 2013 the things are changing. There is uncertainty in the market as share market is showing depression. The bank rate is also increasing. So this study focuses the present factor and future constraints in realestate.

LIMITATION

1. The study is restricted to Coimbatore city only.
2. The number of respondent is restricted to 200 respondents.
3. The consumer preference will not be the same always, it may vary from time to time.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following methodology is used in this study

Area of the study

The survey was conducted in Coimbatore city in Tamil Nadu state. Coimbatore is the second largest district in Tamil Nadu.

Source of data

The study has used both the primary data and secondary data. Field survey method was employed to collect primary data from 200 respondents through a well framed questionnaire. Secondary data were collected through various journals, magazines, websites and newspapers.

Sample design - For the purpose of the study 200 respondents have been chosen in Coimbatore city by using convenience sampling a questionnaire was prepared and administered in person to all the respondents. The information collected have been edited for reliability and consistency and presented in a master table for analysis.

Tools for analysis - Primary data has been analyzed by using Percentage Analysis Method and Average Rank Analysis.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

**TABLE 1
MODE OF ADVERTISEMENT**

S.NO	MODE OF ADVERTISEMENT	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Bill boards	8	4%
2	News paper	36	18%
3	Magazines	20	10%
4	Online	12	6%
5	Television commercial	120	60%
6	Others specify	4	2%
	TOTAL	200	100%

Awareness is created among majority of the respondents about advertisement through television commercial.

TABLE 2
TYPE OF ADVERTISEMENT

S.NO	TYPE OF ADVERTISEMENT	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Hourly program by celebrity	63	31.5%
2	Regularity show	57	28.5%
TOTAL		120	60%

Majority of the respondents watch hourly program by celebrity.

TABLE 3
MESSAGE CONVEYED BY ADVERTISEMENT

S.NO	MESSAGE CONVEYED BY ADVERTISEMENT	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Selling the service	80	40 %
2	Introducing the service and clear vision about services.	71	35.5%
3	Focusing services comparatively cheap prices	49	24.5%
TOTAL		200	100%

Majority of the respondents are feels that advertisement focus to sell the services.

TABLE 4
DESCRIPTION THE ADVERTISEMENT

S.NO	DESCRIBE THE ADVERTISEMENT	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Funny	30	15%
2	Emotional	15	7.5%
3	Informative	84	42%
4	Irritating	17	8.5%
5	Pleasing	23	11.5%
6	Memorable	17	8.5%
7	Boring	14	7%
TOTAL		200	100%

Majority of the respondents indicates the description of the advertisement is informative.

TABLE 5
EFFECTIVENESS OF ADVERTISEMENT

S.NO	EFFECTIVENESS OF ADVERTISEMENT	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Positive impression	57	28.5%
2	Desire to purchase	58	29%
3	Recall	28	14%
4	Interest	57	28.5%
TOTAL		200	100%

Majority of the respondents are desire to purchase because of the effectiveness of advertisement.

TABLE 6
REASON FOR INVESTMENT

S.NO	REASON FOR INVESTMENT	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Tax benefit	29	14.5%
2	Safety of money	59	29.5%
3	Increase of asset	42	21%
4	Expecting a good long term return on investment	49	24.5%
5	Expecting a good short term return on investment	21	10.5%
TOTAL		200	100%

Majority of the respondents invest for the purpose of safety of money.

TABLE 7
PROBLEMS FACED BY REAL ESTATE BUYERS

S.NO	PROBLEMS FACED	NO OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1	Lack of development (Area)	51	25.5%
2	Lack of safety	35	17.5%
3	Overpaying	43	21.5%
4	Documental problem	71	35.5%
TOTAL		200	100%

Majority of the respondents faces documental problems.

TABLE 8
RANKING FOR FACILITIES CONSIDERING IN BUYING REAL ESTATE

S.NO	FACTORS	PERCENTAGE	RANK
1	Water & Electricity	3.27	4
2	Location of land	2.57	1
3	Hospitals, Schools ,Colleges	3.35	5
4	Price	2.86	2
5	Government approval	2.93	3

It is clear from the table ,that facilities considering while buying real estate have given to first rank for location of land, second rank for price, third rank for government approval, fourth rank for water and electricity and fifth rank for hospitals, schools, colleges.

SUGGESTIONS :

Advertisement - From the study it is clear that most of the respondents are aware of a company by means of advertisement. The hourly program in local channels is highly viewed by the respondents. Some of the most well known companies do not take part in advertising. If those companies also advertise their services, there will be growth in the real estate sector.

Legal documental problems - There are people who can produce fake documents to present

themselves as sellers of properties. Before registering your newly acquired property, make sure that all the papers are in order and check it with a person who is efficient in it.

Exploitation of Agricultural land - As there is an increase in population, the people spread to many places. That is, new houses and other buildings are built as per the needs. After occupying the empty lands, the people have started to exploit agricultural lands. The government must stop the growing population from destroying our main source of food by implementing strict rules. The government must encourage agriculture and help the people involved in agriculture for destroying our food source.

Investment - Investing in real estate is one of the main modes of investment. Investing in land or any other property gives huge profits. That is, the property must be purchased in such a way that it gives huge returns.

Reduction in Growth - The real estate is one of the most important and developing sectors in our country. The Indian real estate has played a great role for the increase in our country's GDP. But India's GDP growth for the fourth quarter of 2011-12 came in at a nine-year low of 5.3% taking down the full-year growth to 6.5% from levels of 8.4% seen in 2010-11. Economists assume that the GDP forecasts may drop from 7% levels of 6.5% and below for 2012-13. This reduction in the real estate sector is due to poor conditions of the government. Now a-days people fear to buy properties as they face many problems like duplicate documents, non-payment of property tax etc.

Government and its rules - Indian real estate has several rules and regulations. But neither the public fails to follow the rules or the government does not implement the rules. Stamp duty is extremely high and must be rationalized and brought down to 2-3% as per global practice, which is now in India varies from 13-14%. This discourages the investors due to high cost.

CONCLUSION :

After studying all the factors of the real estate it can be concluded that the Real Estate is a very wide concept and it is highly affected by the advertisements and 60% of people are attracted

by advertisement. Majority of the people are benefited by advertisement because it helps in knowledge the general public on real estate business. People face problems like no government approved price, documental fraudulence, DTP approval, false attention by the advertising channels, etc. Legal issues should also be kept in mind while choosing a property. The present status of agriculture is reducing rapidly. Major drawback in a real estate business is growing by destroying the agricultural sector and destruction of forest area.

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“BIG DATA : UNDERSTANDING THE DYNAMICS OF DATA ECHO SYSTEM”

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Introduction:

Big data is a term applied to a new generation of software, applications, system and storage architecture, all designed to provide business value from unstructured / unbalanced data. Big Data sets require advanced tools, software, and systems to capture, store, manage, and analyze the data sets, all in a timeframe that preserves the intrinsic and use full value of the data.

Much attention is paid to the various services that mobile phone technology has brought to billions / trillions of people in the developing world but now many policy-makers, corporate leaders and development experts are realizing the potential applications, like the examples above, for the enormous amounts of data created by and about the individuals who use these services.

Sources such as online or mobile financial transactions, social media traffic, and GPS coordinates now generate over 2.5 quintillion bytes of called “big data” every day[1], and the growth of mobile data traffic from subscribers in emerging markets is expected to exceed 100% annually through 2015 [2].

Building user centric solutions offers compelling possibilities for providing better access to services in health, education, financial services, and agriculture for people living in poverty. We will see one by one.

Financial Services

Data collected from mobile money services can provide deep insight into spending and saving

habits across sectors and regions. Digital payment histories can allow individuals to build credit histories, making them candidates for loans and other credit based financial services.

Education

Data derived from the use of mobile value added services can be used to improve public sector understanding of educational needs and knowledge gaps, allowing more targeted and timely initiatives to distribute critical information.

Health

Data collected through mobile devices, whether captured by health workers, submitted by individuals or analyzed in the form of data exhaust, can be a crucial tool in understanding population health trends or stopping outbreaks. When collected in the context of individual electronic health records, this data not only improves continuity of care for the individual but it can be used to create massive datasets with which treatments and outcomes can be compared in an efficient and cost effective manner.

Agriculture

Mobile payments for agricultural products, input purchases and allowances may help governments better predict food production trends and incentives. This knowledge can be used to ensure the availability of proper crop storage, reduce waste and spoilage, and provide better information about what types of financial services are needed by farmers. Early detection can help prevent families from leaving their land and further decreasing agricultural production.

Understanding the Dynamics of the Data Ecosystem:

To turn mobile generated data into an economic development tool, a number of ecosystem elements must be in place. For those individuals who generate the data mechanisms must be developed to ensure sufficient user privacy and security. At the same time, business models must be created to provide the proper incentives for

private sector actors to share and use data for the benefit of society. Companies in search and social networking profit from products they offer at no charge to end users because the usage data these products generate is valuable to other ecosystem actors. Similar models could be created in the mobile data sphere, and the data generated through them could maximize the impact of scarce public sector resources by indicating where resources are most needed.

A look at the various types of data and actors in the data ecosystem illustrates the roles and incentives at work. The private sector maintains vast collection of transactional data, much of which is “data exhaust” or data created as a by-product of other transactions. With the use of mobile phones, much of this data can be associated with individuals and their locations. The public sector in most countries also maintains enormous datasets in the form of census data, health indicators, and tax and expenditure information. The graphic below illustrates the various data types, incentives, and requirements of actors in this new data ecosystem.

Closing the Information Gap: Identifying and Analyzing the Data:

A number of organizations in the public and development sectors have embraced the vision of a data ecosystem in which information captured from these varied sources is used for the benefit of global populations. Global Pulse is aimed to bring together expertise from the public, private, development, and academic sectors to develop approaches for harnessing data for policy and action. One of the Director Mr. Robert Kirkpatrick, says that data collected through mobile device usage can encourage effective action in two primary ways:

- 1) By reducing the time lag between the start of a trend and when governments and

other authorities are able to respond to them, and

- 2) By reducing the knowledge gap about how people respond to these trends [5].

Public health offers one of the most significant areas where the analysis of mobile and Internet data could lead to huge public gains.

Employing new data collection and analysis methods could be a less costly, more efficient method of developing market intelligence for large organizations like the World Bank. The Bank already spends millions of dollars each year on statistical analysis of the needs of the poor [3]. Smarter data collection and analysis could free resources for use in economic development efforts [4].

Obstacles on the Path to the Data Commons:

Ecosystem actors, like those described above, have much to gain from the creation of an open data commons. The sharing of such data especially that tied to individuals raises acceptable concerns that must be addressed to achieve this cross sector collaboration.

Privacy and Security - As ecosystem players look to use mobile generated data, they face concerns about violating user trust, rights of expression, and confidentiality. Privacy and security concerns must be addressed before various firms, governments, and individuals also can be convinced to share data more openly.

Data Personalization - When individuals have huge information, it is impossible to aggregate all data from the same individual. This data is most useful if it can be attached to demographic indicators, which allow the data to tell a story about the habits of a segment of the population. Improved methods of tying subscriptions to analytical information are needed to ensure data generated by mobile devices is as individualized as possible.

Data Sharing Incentives - Individuals, fearing security and privacy concerns, often resist sharing personal data. In addition, many private sector firms do not see an incentive to share data they regard as proprietary. Governments often cannot force contractors to share data collected in the execution of public contracts or make all government data available for use by academia, development organizations and companies. All players must see material benefits and incentives in data sharing that repair the risks.

Human Capital - Accurate and actionable data mining and analysis requires considerable technical skill, and data scientists are both in short supply and expensive to employ.

Overcoming the Obstacles:

Novel Approaches - A number of organizations are already working to overcome the challenges and create the incentive structures needed for cross sector co-operation. Global Pulse is creating a network of Pulse Labs that bring together experts in government, academia, the development sector, and private companies to pioneer new approaches to using data for development challenges.

As an example, Athletic apparel company Nike has demonstrated an approach to corporate data sharing through its GreenXchange patent sharing system. Nike is among the first corporations to explore opening up data publicly, and plans to share data on the sustainability of its operations.

In the area of individual incentives, Jana, a Boston-based start-up, conducts market research for global organizations in over 50 countries. The company uses SMS to survey emerging market customers in exchange for airtime, creating a financial incentive for consumers to overcome their concerns about sharing personal data.

Government as Data Catalyst - Several forward thinking governments in the developing world are demonstrating how government can analyze the development of this ecosystem through the opening of its own datasets and the active management of their dissemination and use.

In July 2011, Kenya launched its new Open Data Portal, which includes a full digital edition of the 2009 census, 12 years of detailed government expenditure data, government household income surveys, and the location of schools and health facilities. The portal provides unlimited data access on the web and through mobile phones to researchers, web and software developers, journalists, students, civil society and the general public. Civic organizations, mobile application developers, and media groups are already using the data to improve understanding of population patterns, increase the transparency of governments, and map public services.

Policy frameworks for such protections are now being backfilled. Finch sees the role of government as setting the legal frameworks governing data privacy and security, and also in

developing systems that allow various agencies and ministries to continually update the data they make available. The development community can encourage this behavior by supporting progressive governments such as Kenya's and linking them to the technical and financial resources they need.

Conclusion:

To realize the mutual benefits of creating an environment for sharing mobile generated data, all ecosystem actors must commit to active and open participation. Governments can take the lead in setting policy and legal frameworks that protect individuals and require contractors to make their data public. Development organizations can continue supporting governments and demonstrating both the public good and the business value that data contribution can deliver and the private sector can move faster to create mechanisms for the sharing of data that can benefit the public.

Despite the challenges and risks, the opportunities available to better serve individuals in emerging markets should overcome these risks.

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Entrepreneurship Development for Micro entrepreneurs with special reference to Women entrepreneurs

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INTRODUCTION :

The total working population in India may be divided in - employment & self employment. The employment opportunities are available in the Government, Semi-government & Private sector. The opportunities in government, semi-government sector are very limited in comparison to the private sector. Therefore to increase the rate of working population, we must look forward towards the area of self employment. The success of self employment depends upon the quality of entrepreneurship. It is observed that self employment is generated through small, mini & tiny sector of the industry. The emerging term used for it is Micro Enterprises.

The word 'micro' means small, mini or tiny. Small & Medium Enterprise Development Act (MSMED) 2006 defines it as the enterprises engaged in the manufacturing or production of goods, whose investment in plant & machinery does not exceed Rs. 25 lakh & enterprises engaged in providing or rendering of services, whose investment in equipment does not exceed Rs. 10 lakh. Thus the small manufacturing & service enterprises includes the units like bakery, washing soap, food products, pickle making, beauty parlor, tailoring, embroidery, jewelry designing etc. In all above units women can prove themselves with better performance. The micro enterprises ensure the utilization of local resources & provide additional employment opportunities. Moreover it is one of the most cost effective ways of creating employment. It provides very strong platform for women.

The present condition of this sector is so critical to discourage the upcoming entrepreneurs. The environment of this sector is flooded with challenges & problems. The main areas of challenges are Finance, Competition, Commercial Laws, Transport, Electricity, Water & Labour. The Law of "survival of the fittest" is applicable here very fairly. So to keep the organization live & to face the challenges successfully the head of the

institution need a multi dimensional personality. The failure of any business unit is not only the loss of particular enterprise & entrepreneur but it's a national loss. If it is repeated frequently it turns into decreasing the economic growth rate in long term. Therefore it is the duty of the Nation to prevent the failure of any business unit. Therefore multi dimensional entrepreneurs are the assets of the Nation. It is the duty & responsibility of specially the commerce education to create such personalities from the institute.

LITERATURE REVIEW :

1) Dipanjan Chakarborty and Ratan Broman "The basic rationale of developing microenterprises is that they provide additional employment opportunities and ensure more equitable distribution of income and better standard of living. It is most cost effective way of creating employment. Introduction of entrepreneurship in school and college education can help faster entrepreneurial culture right from the beginning. Appropriate technological guidance will make the production process easier. Entrepreneurship business development cell needs to be established at village level and entrepreneurship guidance and counseling cell must function to motivate entrepreneurs in rural areas."

The Role of microenterprises in the promotion of Rural Entrepreneurship in Assam. Page No. 7

The IUP journal of Entrepreneurship Development Vol. IX - No-3 September 2012

2) K. Nagarajan- "Entrepreneurs are the backbones of any economy. Therefore it is necessary to nurture the quality of entrepreneurship among the people & to avoid entrepreneurial failures. The key reason of the failure is the lack of awareness of market forces."

Predominance of Market Forces in Entrepreneurial Failures - Page No. 22.

The IUP journal of Entrepreneurship Development Vol. IX - No-3 September 2012

3) E.M. Reji - "The experience of women

self help groups suggests that it is possible to capitalize on the strength of the group to promote enterprise among the poor. The credit facilities made available with bank linkage programme helped the members to have access to credit at affordable interest and easy terms and conditions. A few years of experience with the enterprise activities helped those members to build confidence and start income generating activities.”

Group Entrepreneurship for creating successful Microenterprises - Page No. 33.

The IUP journal of Entrepreneurship Development Vol. IX - No-3 September 2012

4) Indranil Mutsuddi - “Orienting students towards entrepreneurship should be one of the strategic goals for every technical institution and business school. For achieving such goal every institute should aim to encourage their students and faculty members to start E-cell, involve entrepreneurs, corporate leaders, consultants, academicians and researchers to create a nurturing environment on campuses by which students could be mentored for developing entrepreneurial capabilities.”

Relevance of Entrepreneurship cells in Technical Institutes and Business school- Page No. 58.

The IUP journal of Entrepreneurship Development Vol. IX - No-3 September 2012

5) U. Mallikarjunaiah & K. Sudarsan - “Many problems faced by the fishermen were in the area of finance, material, production, fishing crafts and gears, marketing and other infrastructure required by them. So the government should encourage the fishing community through providing the essential minimum education. This would reduce the disappointment among the youth, and they would become self-reliant and self confident.”

Problems of Fishermen in Nellore District of Andhra Pradesh - Page No. 27.

Prabandhan Indian Journal of Management July 2012 - ISSN - 0975 - 2854.

6) S. Tarakeswara Rao G. Tulasi Rao, M.P. Suri Ganesh - “The women should be provided with adequate training in development of entrepreneurial skills covering management of enterprises, maintaining account, enhancing

productivity, marketing, selling etc. So that they can undertake income generating activities.”

A Study on the performance of Micro Enterprises In Srikaklan - District, Andhra Pradesh.

Management of Micro Enterprises - Page No. 35 - Prabandhan - Indian Journal of Management July 2012 ISSN-0975 2894.

7) Meenu Singh - “In the changing context of emergence of knowledge economy, higher education institutions need to embrace the concept of lifelong education and training.” Higher Education challenges in New Era - Page No. 21. - University News 50 (39) September 24-30-2012- ISSN-0566-2257.

8) Vaidyanathan Shivkumar - “We must have life building, man making, character making, assimilation of ideas and that is the purpose of our quality education.”

Quality in Indian Higher Education Problems & its possible solutions, Page 52. Univer. New 50 (43) Oct. 22-28, 2012 - ISSN-0566-2257.

9) S. Jeelani- “There is strong need for consolidation and strengthening our higher education system by addressing the issues like faculty appointment, curriculum upgrading, quality of education, employable education, providing professional education at lower costs.”

Strengthening Higher Education System in India- Page No. 56. University News, 50 (43) October 22-28-2012 - ISSN-0566-2257.

10) Janak M. Shah and Padma Sedani - “In spite of being the third largest faculty in terms of students enrollment, faculty of commerce has not been viewed with high regards by the society in general & commerce & industry in particular.”

Re-Thinking Commerce Education- Page No. 21. University News 50 (43) November 19-25, 2012. ISSN - 0566 - 2257.

11) D. A. Ghanchi - “The higher education system needs to look forward in the (1) Areas of responsible, conscientious citizenship (2) Area of Sensitive game changing leadership (3) Area of competent production, discipline & passionate workmanship (4) Area of bold, calculating and progressive entrepreneurship.

India's Higher Education : How It can build up the Nations soft power Page No. 9.

University News 50 (33) August 13-19, 2012 - ISSN - 0566 - 2257

From the above review it is clear that micro enterprise plays a very important role in the economy. But facing number of problems for their survival. For the development of micro-entrepreneurship it is suggested that education regarding entrepreneurship along with technological guidance and appropriate skill should be provided. This responsibility should be born by the Higher Education sector. Establishment of entrepreneurship cell in college is also suggested. The women should be provided with adequate training in development of entrepreneurial skill. The area on which education department should focused is entrepreneurship development through awareness of market forces, finance, marketing, etc. to avoid the disappointment among the youth and make them self reliant and self confident.

OBJECTIVES :

The main object of this paper is to determine the role of commerce education in the development of Micro Entrepreneurship with special reference to women. The other objectives are: -

- * To study the socio - economic profile of the girl student in B. Com. Course.
- * To study the nature & profile of the Micro Enterprises run specially by women in Indore.
- * To analyze the view of girl students towards establishing own business unit.
- * To study various problems faced by women entrepreneurs.
- * To determine the role of commerce education in promoting the Micro Women Entrepreneurship.

METHODOLOGY :

There are three categories to be considered for the purpose of study, namely -Women Entrepreneurs, Girl students from B.Com. Course & Faculties of commerce colleges at Indore.

For the First category -10 small business units which are totally run by only women were selected. The list of units is - (1) Beauty Parlor (2) Pickle Making Unit (3) Tailoring Shop (stitching suit & blouse) (4) Embroidery Unit (5)

Microwave Cooking Class (6) Jewellery Designing (7) Tiffin Centre (8) Mahanadi Designing (9) Readymade Garment Shop (10) Soft Toys Shop. The total sample size in this category was 50. The necessary information was collected by an interview method.

For the second category, the student doing only B.Com. From DAVV are considered. Those students offering other courses with B.Com. Like CA, CS or preparing for competitive exams. are not included in sample. The sample size in this category was 100. The necessary information was collected by Questioner method.

The information & opinion regarding commerce education was collected from faculties of commerce of different colleges at Indore.

The other necessary information was collected from published information. Thus in this paper, the primary & secondary data both are used to draw the conclusion.

KEY FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

A) Woman Entrepreneurs - The various problems discussed by the Woman Entrepreneurs are as follows-

Finance- Regarding finance the problems disclosed are-

- * Lack of sufficient capital & inadequate working capital.
- * Inadequate information about loan & other facilities provided by Govt.
- * Burden of shop rent & interest on loan.
- * Improper accounting system .

Marketing- The problems in this regard are-

- * Lack of marketing.
- * Inadequate market research.
- * Lack of awareness about market changes.

Competition- The competition faced by these business women-

- * Within the same type & size of unit.
- * With big business units.
- * With upcoming mall & retail outlets by business tycoons.

Other problems- The other problems emerged during discussion are-

- * The insufficient knowledge & skill put them on the back foot.

- * Labour problem.
- * Lack of support from other family members.
- * Burdon of house hold work alongwith business.

Almost all the respondent are not ready to suggest their relatives to come in the business without proper training & knowledge.

B) The Girl Students- To know the level of awareness, interest & their requirement, the survey was conducted. The findings are-

- * 40% of respondent wants to become a teacher.
- * 10% of respondent are ready to start their business.
- * 20% of respondent will decide after getting some primary information.
- * Remaining respondent are totally blank on the issue of starting any business.
- * 10% student from the sample has their family business of readymade garments & restaurant. But they don't want to join their family business.
- * The interest shown by the student in the business like Beauty Parlor, Boutique, Artificial Jewellery Shop & Coaching Class.

The problems of student are-

- 1) Hesitation 2) Disappointment
- 3) Lack of knowledge 4) Lack of confidence
- 5) Socio -economic problems
- 6) Problem of security & protection
- 7) Requirement of training
- 8) Narrow thinking of the family members

C) Educator's Opinion- On the issue of entrepreneurship development through commerce education, the different opinion of educator's are -

- * More than 70% of commerce graduates are not employable.
- * Effective industrial training is needed along with degree.
- * Industrial tie-up should be given priority.
- * Along with job oriented education, Entrepreneurship oriented education shall be provided.
- * The present course structure is not competent to generate entrepreneurs.
- * The training & skill development programme should be added in course.

On the basis of findings, it is observed that

the key reasons of women entrepreneurs are lack of knowledge, skill & market awareness. The upcoming female entrepreneurs need more knowledge, training & protection along with developed personality. On the other hand present course structure of commerce is not enough to build entrepreneurs. In fact it is not even competent to provide any job to the graduates. In this regard Hon'able Dr. Kalam has rightly said that "India's real problem is not unemployment but, unemployability."

SUGGESTIONS :

On the basis of above findings, we put forth some suggestions for the growth & development of Women Micro Entrepreneurship-

Establishment of Entrepreneurship Cell- Every college should establish this cell like Placement Cell. The NAAC Team, at the time of accreditation should insist the college to establish this cell. The duties & responsibilities of this cell should be-

- * To generate total information regarding Micro Business.
- * To create Self Help Groups.
- * To establish industrial tie-up with college
- * To organize Entrepreneurship Development Programmes, Training Programmes, to provide Consultancy for upcoming entrepreneurs in the college. To provide information regarding Govt. policies & facilities meant for women entrepreneurs.
- * To develop market awareness & to undertake Market research.

Personality Development Programme

It should include training regarding-

Communication Skill Positive Thinking
Morality & Ethics External Personality

Quality Development Programme

5 Q's are needed to be developed among the students-

- * I.Q = Intelligences Quality
- * E.Q. - Emotional Quality
- * K.Q. - Knowledge Quality
- * L.Q.- Leadership Quality
- * S.Q. - Social Quality

Based on the discussion & issues raised in this paper, it can be concluded that woman micro entrepreneurship is an emerging concept. It plays a vital roll in acceraleting the working population from poor section of the society as well as

economic development. But the present scenario of business & society is some how discouraging for the development of woman micro entrepreneurship. To encourage them colleges providing commerce education should come forward. These colleges should help specially the girl student from middle & lower sections of the society. They should try to develop confidence, positive attitude & motivate the upcoming young entrepreneurs. If it is done successfully then the employability will automatically generate in the economy. It is the economic independence which will relive women from all the sorrows & make them happy.

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Metropolitan Cities and Migration: An Indian Scenario

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Introduction:

Metropolitan cities all over the world are growing in size and becoming denser as a result of rapid urbanization, India too is line with other nations in this regard. These cities are considered as vital economical, cultural and political nerve centers of the country. Further these cities are also regarded as a crucial hub for regional or international associations and communications. Census of India (2001) defines metropolitan cities “as one possessing a population of more than 40 lakh (4 million). The growth of metropolitan cities is also affected by migration, which is from the other parts of the country as well as from the other countries. In India, people migrate from rural to urban areas mainly due to poverty, high population pressure on the land, lack of

basic infrastructural facilities like health care, education, etc. Migration is a process which implies a permanent or at least semi-permanent change in place of residence of an individual from one location to another. According to the definition given by Census of India (2001) there are seven metropolitan cities in India which are, Greater Mumbai, Kolkata, Delhi, Chennai, Hyderabad, Bangalore, Ahmadabad. The population of these metropolitan cities ranges between 16434386 (Greater Mumbai) to 4525013 (Ahmadabad).

These metropolitan cities are big industrial centers of the country and also known for its information technology like Bangalore is known as Silicon Valley of the country. The city has a software technology park and other institutions like Indian Institute of Science etc. Likewise, Mumbai is considered as the financial capital of India and it is one of the world’s fourth major metropolitan agglomerations. New Delhi is known for its fastest growing industries of the country. Kolkata is the third largest city and urban agglomeration in India. Chennai is the fourth largest metropolitan area in India and the capital of the Indian state Tamil Nadu. Hyderabad is the

capital of Andhra Pradesh and a port city. Ahmadabad is the largest city in Gujarat which is located on the bank of Sabarmati River and is regarded as the largest island business centre in western region of the country.

Growth Rate of Metropolitan Cities:

Table 1 reveals the population growth rate of metropolitan cities during 1991-2001. The growth rate of metropolitan cities in India has increased during the period 1991-2001 and is ranging from 53.0 percent in Delhi to 19.8 percent in Kolkata. The fastest growth rate is recorded in Delhi i.e. 53 percent, which is known for its fastest growing industries. After Delhi, Bangalore occupies the second place. Kolkata has the lowest growth rate during 1991-2001.

Table : 1

Metropolitan Cities: Population Growth Rate

Metropolitan Cities	State	1991	2001	1991-2001
		Population	Population	Growth rate (in percent)
Delhi	Delhi	8419084	12877470	53.0
Bangalore	Karnataka	4130288	5701446	38.0
Ahmadabad	Gujarat	3312216	4525013	36.6
Hyderabad	Andhra Pradesh	4344437	5742036	32.2
Greater Mumbai	Maharashtra	12596243	16434386	30.5
Chennai	Tamil Nadu	5421985	6560242	21.0
Kolkata	West Bengal	11021918	13205697	19.8

Source: Census of India 1991, 2001.

Migration Streams in Metropolitan Cities:

There are mainly two migration streams in metropolitan cities which are:

- Rural to Urban Migration.
- Urban to Urban Migration.

Table: 2
Metropolitan Cities: Migration Streams

Metropolitan Cities	Rural to Urban Migrants			Urban to Urban Migrants		
	Persons	Male	Female	Persons	Male	Female
Greater Mumbai	65.1	67.8	61.4	28.8	26.6	32.0
Delhi	58.6	61.6	54.8	29.9	27.3	33.3
Kolkata	46.6	47.8	45.1	18.7	17.2	20.3
Hyderabad	46.3	47.4	45.1	30.5	30.5	30.5
Bangalore	39.9	41.3	38.2	39.9	38.9	41.1
Chennai	37.8	38.9	36.7	33.1	32.9	33.4
Ahmadabad	54.8	55.4	54.2	25.7	24.5	26.9

Source: Census of India (2001), Migration Tables, D-3(UAS/Cities).

Note: The aggregate of the streams does not tally to 100.00 as place of last residence unclassified as rural or urban is included in total migrants.

Rural to urban migration stream carry rural people towards growing urban centers. Table 2 shows that the share of rural to urban migrants is more than urban to urban migrants in all metropolitan cities. People come in urban centers, from rural areas in search of work and employment and also from urban areas to improve their job prospects. The highest percentage of rural to urban migrants is found in Mumbai, which is considered as the financial hub and financial capital of India. It is also one of the world's fourth major metropolitan agglomerations. After Mumbai, Delhi is the second dominant metropolitan city which attracts migrants from rural areas. Delhi is considered as an imperative commercial centre of South Asia. The key service industries of Delhi include telecommunication, information technology, banking, media, hotels and tourism. On the other hand, the high proportion of urban to urban migrants is found in Bangalore, which is 39.9 percent. Bangalore is known its software technology park and provides employment to skilled persons only.

Reasons for migration in Metropolitan Cities:

“It is possible to know the broad reasons of migration from the census since 1981 census. The same list of reasons continued in 1991 and 2001 census as well except that the reason ‘Business’ was added in 1991 and the reason ‘Natural Calamities’ was dropped out from the list in 2001. An additional reason of ‘moved after birth’ was added in 2001 census” (Bhagat, 2009). Census of India (2001) classified the ‘reasons of migration’

into seven categories viz. employment, business, education, marriage, moved after birth, moved with household and others, Which included movement due to displacement, retirement etc. It is observed from table 3 that employment is the major reason for migration in metropolitan cities. In Delhi, Mumbai and Bangalore mostly migrants are coming from rural areas in search of employment and work. All these metropolitan cities are growing fastly due to establishment of industries in these areas which attract a large number of migrants in search of work. In Kolkata, Ahmadabad, Hyderabad and Chennai other reasons play an important role.

Table:3

Reasons of Migration in Metropolitan Cities, 2001

Million cities	Employment	Business	Education	Marriage	Moved After Birth	Moved With household	Others
Delhi	34.84	0.73	1.45	15.2	2.31	33.13	12.34
Kolkata	21.54	2.66	1.46	19.72	3.44	20.53	30.65
Ahmadabad	17.44	6.63	0.86	18.06	6.86	24.35	25.8
Greater Mumbai	36.3	0.95	1.51	19.6	9.32	17.81	14.5
Hyderabad	25.03	2.61	2.64	9.94	3.68	21.59	34.51
Bangalore	28.47	2.12	3.02	15.68	4.72	17.6	28.39
Chennai	21.63	1.58	1.83	12.58	4.32	19.72	38.34
Rural Migrants							
Delhi	41.34	0.42	0.99	14.28	2.08	33.56	7.32
Kolkata	29.94	3.22	1.58	23.87	3.31	22.85	15.24
Ahmadabad	22.99	8.12	0.96	21.76	7.62	27.48	11.08
Greater Mumbai	40.93	0.8	1.39	19.45	8.69	16.78	11.96
Hyderabad	34	2.7	2.94	12.65	3.99	26.24	17.48
Bangalore	39.01	2.23	2.76	19.13	4.68	19.38	12.82
Chennai	30.55	2.05	1.7	17.62	5.2	24.02	18.86
Urban Migrants							
Delhi	27.24	1.38	2.56	19.02	2.94	36.18	10.68
Kolkata	18.2	3.35	2.26	24.4	5.68	28.24	17.88
Ahmadabad	17.19	7.84	1.18	21.59	9.01	30.6	12.59
Greater Mumbai	29.91	1.35	1.92	21.69	11.15	21.3	12.67
Hyderabad	27.35	4.03	3.75	11.82	4.75	26.34	21.96
Bangalore	30.52	2.91	4.58	18.75	6.22	22.53	14.49
Chennai	26.34	2.1	3.22	15.19	5.78	26.7	20.67

Source: Census of India (2001), Migration Tables, D-3(UAS/Cities).

Conclusion: The growth rate of metropolitan cities in India has increased during the period 1991-2001. As far as migration streams are concerned share of rural to urban migrants is more than urban to urban migrants in all the metropolitan cities. Employment is the major reason for migration in metropolitan cities.

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Right to Information and Good Governance

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INTRODUCTION

Secrecy in government is the most important cause of corruption, inefficiency and irresponsiveness and an enemy to Good Governance. In addition to other measure made available to people Right to Information Act 2005 is a landmark achievement as through this corrupt politicians and bureaucracy would be exposed and there is a hope to develop a clean public life. RTI Act 2005 will strengthen democracy and would usher an era of socialistic pattern of society.

‘Good governance’ means the efficient and effective administration in a democratic framework. It involves high level organizational efficiency and effectiveness corresponding in a responsive manner in order to attain the predetermined desirable goals of society. According to the World Bank document entitled ‘Governance and Development (1992)’, the parameters of good governance are as follows:

1. Legitimacy of the political system.
2. Freedom of association and participation by various social, economic, religious, cultural and professional groups in the process of governance.
3. An established legal framework based on the rule of law and independence of judiciary to protect human rights, secure social justice and guard against exploitation and abuse of power.
4. Bureaucratic accountability including transparency in administration.
5. Freedom of information and expression required for formulation of public policies, decision-making, monitoring and evaluation of government performance.
6. A sound administrative system leading to efficiency and effectiveness.
7. Co-operation between government and civil society organizations.

Similar principles have been enunciated by the OECD, which emphasizes on legitimate

government, accountability of political and official elements of government, competence of government to make policy and deliver services; and respect for human rights and rule of law.

In light of the above, if one were to venture a list of parameters that go into determination of the quality of governance, the major factors would include limited government, legitimacy of the government, political and bureaucratic accountability, freedom of information and expression, transparency and cost effective administration, established legal framework based on rule of law for protecting the human life, securing social justice and checking abuse of power.

The access to information is cardinal to good Governance and access to information is a vital factor for achieving the goals of good Governance. For it promotes transparency and public accountability in the working of Govt. functionaries.

To be precise, the right to information is indeed the master key to good governance since it helps to:

- Promote openness, transparency and accountability in public service;
- Empower people to combat state corruption;
- Prevent administrative highhandedness or arbitrariness;
- Bridge the gap between provider and recipient of public service;
- Make citizens part of the decision-making process in the government;
- Provide responsive administration;
- Strengthen the foundation of grassroots democracy through people’s participation in local governance and development activities; and
- Empower people to have access to other rights.

Public Accountability and Right to Information:

‘Public Accountability’ is a facet of administrative efficiency. Publicity of information serves as an instrument for the

oversight of citizens. By the same token it suggests that law could become a means for fighting corruption. Therefore, a government which produces a trustworthy flow of information creates greater certainty and transparency. So that public Accountability is a part of Good Governance. This is especially appreciated by those who intend to invest in the country. International experience shows that countries that allow citizens to access public information have seen a reduction in indicators of corruption and, consequently, substantial increase in administrative efficiency. 'Public Accountability' is a part of Governance. It is the Government that is accountable to the public for delivering a broad set of outcomes but more importantly it is the public service consisting of public servants that constitutes the delivery mechanism. Therefore, the accountability and governance arrangements between government which acts as the principal and the public service which is its agent, impact on the government's ability to deliver and on its accountability to the public. The challenge lies in ensuring that the public service is geared to meet the expectations of the government of the day and that public service is neutral, whichever party is in power. When a government department translates a government's policy into programmes, the success of that translation is very much dependent on a clear understanding of and commitment to the outcomes that are sought. It is not surprising that the history of accountability and governance within the public service has shifted from measuring "inputs" to measuring "outputs", to matching outputs, and identify outcomes. The key which weakens accountability or the effectiveness of the government or the public sector is the lack of information.

The World Bank, for the first time in 1989, highlighted the concept of good governance. By good governance, it meant, sound public management, and in this context, identified four dimensions:

- i. Public sector management;
- ii. Accountability;
- iii. Legal framework for development; and
- iv. Information and transparency

In 1992, the Bank's document Governance and

Development said, "Good governance is central to creating and sustaining an environment which fosters strong and equitable development and it is an essential complement to sound economic policies". While saying so the document identified three aspects of governance:

- i. The form of political regime;
- ii. The process by which authority is exercised in the management of country's economic and social resources; and
- iii. The capacity of governments to design, formulate and implement policies and, in general, to discharge government functions.

In essence, to World Bank, good governance consists of;

1. Political Accountability;
2. Regular elections to legitimize the exercise of political powers.
3. Participations by various social, economic, cultural and professional groups in the process of governance;
4. Rule of law;
5. Independence of judiciary;
6. Bureaucratic accountability;
7. Freedom of Information;
8. Transparency;
9. Efficient and effective administrative system; and
10. Co-operation between government and the civil society.

Administrative Efficiency and Right to Information:

Although efficiency in the private sector may be judged in solely economic terms, it cannot be so simply evaluated in the public sphere of government. Unlike the business community, the purpose of government is not to generate profits. Government has many duties in society including the allocation of scarce resources and the provision of social services such as health care, and its efficiency must be evaluated in broader, more distinct terms than profits and losses. Furthermore, government is constrained by the public in terms of what is desired and what will be

tolerated in ways that agents of the private sector are not. The government is accountable to the people and, therefore, goals cannot be set by the government alone; Government has to keep the citizens satisfied or at least pacified.

Recommendations of Second Administrative Reforms Commission:

Civil Services Rules of all States may be reworded on the following lines:

“Communication of Official Information:

Every Government servant shall, in performance of his duties in good faith, communicate to a member of public or any organization full and accurate information, which can be disclosed under the Right to Information Act, 2005.

Explanation – Nothing in this rule shall be construed as permitting communication of classified information in an unauthorized manner or for improper gains to a Government servant or others.”

CONCLUSION :

Right to Information Act is revolutionary and practical and can be used directly and indirectly for administrative and make efforts to improve the health of the administrative system.

As observed in the first Report of Second Administrative Refotm Commission, “The Right to Information Law of 2005 signals a redicial shift in our governance culture and permanently impacts all agencies of state. The effective implementation of this law depends on three fundamental shifts: from the prevailing culture of secrecy to a new culture of openness; from personalized despotism to authority coupled with accountability; and form unilateral decision-making to participative governance”. It is well recognized that right to information is necessary, but not sufficient, to improve governance. A lot more needs to be done to usher in accountability in governance, including protection of whistle blowers, decentralization of power and fushion of authority with accountability at all levels.

Right to Information has been seen as the key to strengthen participatory democracy and ushering in people-centered governance, access

to Information can empower the poor and the weaker sections of society to demand and get Information about public policies and action, thereby leading to their welfare. Without good governance, no amount of developmental schemes can bring in improvements in the quality of life of the citizens; good governance has four elements, transparency, accountability, predictability and participation. In a fundamental sense, right to information is a basic necessity of good governance. Therefore, right to information has also been said to be life blood or democracy. The more the citizen is able to access governmental functioning the greater is the responsiveness of the governmental system to the community needs.

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SELF- HELP GROUPS AND WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN ASSAM

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Introduction :

The biggest challenge to any civilized society is the economic deprivation of the poor. The most potential tool against human deprivation is building of human capital among the deprived. Self-realization and self-initiatives are the two weapons to wash poverty out from the map of the world. According to a world Bank in 1995, the formal financial system reaches only top 25 percent of the economically active population. In India, these financial institutions have not been able to reach the poor households and particularly the women in unorganized sector. The global summit on micro finance held in Washington in February 1997 set a global target of covering 100 million poor families with credit by 2005. It was expected that 20-30 million of these would be only in India.

The concept of self- Help Groups (SHG) got a major impetus after the central government launched the swarnajayanti Gram swarozgar yojana (SGSY) a programme aimed at bringing families above the poverty line by insuring sustainable level of income over a period of time. In Assam, under SGSY 1, 24,719 SHGs have been formed with 22,659 SHGs linked up with banks.

A self- help group (SHG) is a set of people coming together to work for common purpose and membership of the group is decided by themselves. The member of the group may be women or men or composition of both men and women. A SHG may normally have 10-20 members. The members of the group should have a common need and goal to improve their social and economic condition. The primary objectives of the SHG are to grow the habits of savings among the community to enable people to pool their own resources in the form of their savings in order to create financially viable and sustainable revolving loan fund for meeting their credit need.

Objectives of the study :

1. To study the Role of SHGs in women empowerment in Assam.
2. To study the constraints faced by the members of SHGs
3. To provide some valuable suggestions for the upliftment of SHGs.

Methodology :

Methodology is a part and parcel in social research.

The method followed in the present study is mainly based on secondary data i.e. news papers, magazines, periodicals, journals, Seminars and different form of written sources. Random sample observation has also been tried out to focus on the outcome of some SHGs supplemented by govt. report publication in Assam.

Assam at Glance - Assam is a one of the eight states of North East India. It is the largest state in the region in terms of population and second to Arunachal Pradesh in geographical area. In spite of her rich natural resources and culture the state is lagging behind the rest of the country. The socio economic setup of the state has not been conducive to overall development. Since it is a multiethnic state with heterogeneous cultural backgrounds, it has been experiencing insurgency and ethnic strife for the last three decades because of which not only its economy but also the social fabric is under threat. The worst victims in the process are the women. The entire region including Assam is free from some of the social evils like dowry , sati- pratha, female feticide and infanticide because of the prevalence of tribal and indigenous culture. According to Assam Human Development Report (HDR) 2003, the state lagged behind Manipur, Meghalaya, Arunachal Pradesh, Mizoram and Nagaland. Keeping these points of view it is thought to undertake an in depth study on the status of women and their empowerment in the state.

Women empowerment - The term ‘empowerment’ refers to increasing the spiritual, political, social, racial, educational gender or economic strength of individuals and communities. At the Millennium summit in 2000, the 189 member states of the United Nations made a commitment in the Millennium Declaration to achieve 8 goals, labeled the Millennium Development Goal (MDGs). The third goal on this list seeks to achieve gender equality and the empowerment of women. In setting this goal, the U.N member states recognized the contributions that women make to economic development and the costs to societies of the multiple disadvantages that women face in nearly every country.

Role of SHGs in empowerment of women in Assam :

Self- Help Groups (SHGs) dominate the microfinance scenario and it is focusing more on poor women. Hence micro finance is emerging as a powerful

instrument for empowerment of poor women both socially and economically. It aims at providing cost effective mechanism for financial services to the unreached poor women. Rural women in Assam are provided credit and extension support for various production oriented income generating activities. These activities usually include garment making, weaving and knitting. It is seen that 61 percent of total SHGs formed from 1999 to 2006 were women SHGs which was reduced to 5.19 percent during 2006-2007 in the state. Percentage of women SHGs to total SHGs from 1999 to 2006 was observed to be highest in upper Assam i.e. 68%. Central and lower Assam showed poor performance as compared to upper Assam in this respect. On an average central Assam districts had highest number of SHGs formed since 1999 followed by lower Assam and upper Assam. Average number of Assam as compared to lower Assam and central Assam it was highest in central Assam. During the year 2008-2009 total number of SHGs formed in Assam was 2186915754 numbers of women SHGs were 15754. out of 15754 numbers of women SHGs 8073 had taken up economic activities in the same year.

A Brief Review of some women SHGs of Assam:

To justify the above discussed components of empowerment of women through SHGs an attempt has been made to review on some sample example of SHGs supplied by the report of the survey of self-employment project conducted by govt. of Assam 2007.

The survey report covers the study over 100 villages in all 11 districts of Assam and carries out 225 sample survey. It is found that 58% of the SHGs member are agree that SHG bring out the prosperity in their life. Out of the 225 sample 50% of SHGs are women SHG and above brought positive effect on their status. Primarily in Assam women SHGs are considerably successful enough in some income generating sectors such as handloom, poultry, dicker and in some cases women are successful in cultivation also. For example, Chandramukhi SHG of Tinkhang cluster of Duliajan, which is all women member SHG produced a tractor under the Jibonjyoti Yojana of the Govt. of India, have the capability of cultivating 50 bighas of land, thus this SHG stood forward as an example in the male dominated income generating field.

All the story of SHGs in the survey shows that this movement has facilitate discernible economic growth for individual upliftment and now women command greater responsibility in the society. The

membership of SHG also bring a positive change in their life style.

Suggestions :

In order to improve women empowerment through self-Help Groups (SHGs) I would like to suggest some suggestions.

1. Introduction of self-employment programme is not sufficient enough. There should be proper supervision inspection and guidance for its sound implementation so that women can be self-employed to desired level.
2. Proper training facilities should be provided by the government, NGOs and other institutions to the rural women to be self-employed.
3. The Govt. & NGOs should help women participations in self-employment programmes.
4. Motivation on the part of women regarding productive activities should be improved by NABARD, SIRD & NIRD in effective manner.
5. Government should introduce various small - scale and cottage industries in which women can participation.

Conclusion :

It is seen that SHG movement are playing an important role in improving the status of women and empowering women especially in rural India. SHG has positively contributed for the development of women. For further growth and better performance of SHG, the state, the civil society, groups, NGOs and the international community all have to intervene in promoting SHG. By opening public deliberations, greater involvement could be enhanced. For creating positive attitude and faith on SHG, awareness among the rural women is necessary.

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A STUDY ON QUALITY OF WORK LIFE OF EMPLOYEES IN CONTEMPORARY MANAGEMENT

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Introduction :

A high quality of work life (QWL) is essential for organizations to continue to attract and retain employees. The term QWL gained importance in the late 1960s as a way of concerns about effects of job/work on health and general well-being and ways to positively influence the quality of a person's work experience. Up until the mid 1970s, employers concern was on work design and working conditions improvement. However, in the next decade of 1980s, the concept of QWL included other aspects that affect employees' job satisfaction and productivity and these aspects are, reward systems, physical work environment, employee involvement, rights and esteem needs (Cummings and Worley, 2005).

However the radical changes in the world of business, like factors such as globalization, information technology, world business competitiveness, and scarcity of natural resources have changed employee's outlook of how a good company is defined. The trend in past was to include, financial figures in defining "a good company". Latest trends like, ethics, quality of work life (QWL) and job satisfaction are now considered important predictors of sustainability and viability of business organizations.

According to the American Society of Training and Development, "QWL Is a process of work organization which enables its members at all levels to participate actively and effectively in shaping the organization's environment, methods and outcome". Richard E Walton, states a much broader concept of QWL proposing eight conceptual categories viz. adequate and fair compensation, safe and healthy working conditions, opportunity to use and develop human capacities, future opportunity for continued growth and security, social integration in the work place, social relevance of work, balanced role of work in the total life space and Constitutionalism in the Work Organization etc. it is rare to find work-life situations that satisfy all

eight criteria.

Quality of Work Life denotes all the organizational inputs which aim at employee satisfaction and enhancing organizational effectiveness. Quality of Work Life is a process by which an organization responds to employee needs for developing mechanisms to allow them to share fully in making the decisions that design their lives at work. The term refers to the favorableness or unfavorableness of a total job environment for people. QWL programs are another way in which organizations recognize their responsibility to develop jobs and working conditions that are excellent for people as well as for economic health of the organization. The elements in a typical QWL program include – open communications, equitable reward systems, a concern for employee job security and satisfying careers and participation in decision making. Many early QWL efforts focus on job enrichment. In addition to improving the work system, QWL programs usually emphasize development of employee skills, the reduction of occupational stress and the development of more co-operative labor-management relations

QUALITY OF WORK LIFE

The most comprehensive and widely - quoted definition of QWL was developed by Richard Walton (1974a), who proposed eight major conceptual categories as a framework for analyzing and assessing the phenomenon

1. Adequate and fair compensation - Does pay received meet socially determined standards of sufficiency of the recipient's subjective standard? Does pay received for certain work bear an appropriate relationship to pay received for other work
2. Safety and healthy environment - The employees should not be exposed to physical conditions or work arrangements that are unduly hazardous or unhealthy is widely accepted. In the future, when health will be less the issue than comfort, more stringent standards that today's will possible be imposed, these may include minimizing odors, noise, or visual annoyances.
3. Development of human capacities - To varying degrees work has become fractionated, deskilled, and tightly controlled; planning the work is often separated from implementing it. So jobs differ in how much they enable the worker to use and develop his skills and knowledge, which affects his involvement, self-esteem, and the challenge obtained from the work itself.
4. Growth and security - Attention needs to be given to (a) the extent to which the worker's assignments contribute to maintaining and expanding his capabilities, rather than leading to his obsolescence; (b) the degree to which expanded or newly acquired knowledge & skills can be utilized in future work assignments; and(c) the availability of opportunities to advance in organizational or career terms which peers, family members, or associated recognize.
5. Social Integration - Whether the employee achieves personal identity and self-esteem is influenced by such attributes in the climate of his workplace as freedom from prejudice, a sense of community, interpersonal openness, the absence of

stratification in then organization, and the existence of upward mobility.

6. Constitutionalism - What rights does the worker have and how can he (or she) protect these rights? Wide variations exist in the extent to which the organization culture respects personal privacy, tolerates dissent, adheres to high standards of equity in distributing rewards, and provided for due process in all work-related matters.
7. The total life space - A person's work should have a balanced role in his life. This role encompasses schedules, career demands, and travel requirements that take a limited portion of the person's leisure and family time, as well as advancement and promotion that do not require repeated geographical moves.
8. Social relevance - Organization acting in a socially irresponsible manner causes increasing numbers of these employees to depreciate the value of their work and careers. For example, does the worker perceive disposal, marketing techniques, employment practices, and participation in political campaigns?

Objectives of QWL

- To improve the standard of living of the employees
- To increase the productivity
- To create a positive attitude in the minds of the employees
- To increase the effectiveness of the organization (profitability, goal accomplishment etc)

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

1. Hackman and Oldham (1976) [14] observed psychological growth needs as crucial determinant of Quality of working life. Several such needs were identified; Skill variety, Task Identity, Task significance, Autonomy and Feedback. They concluded that fulfillment of these needs plays an important role if employees are to experience high quality of working life.
2. Taylor (1979) [31] suggested Quality of

working life as an holistic approach that includes; basic extrinsic job factors of wages, hours and working conditions, and the intrinsic job notions of the nature of the work itself. He also viewed other aspects to be equally important such as; authority exercised by employees, employee participation in decision making, fair and equal approach at work, social support, utilizing one's present skills, self growth, a relevant scope of future at work, social relevance of the work or product, effect on extra work activities. Taylor concluded that Quality of working life policies may vary as per the size of organization and employee group.

3. Warr and colleagues (1979) [33], in their survey for Quality of working life, considered a variety of factors resulting in QWL, including work involvement, intrinsic job motivation, higher order need strength, perceived intrinsic job characteristics, job satisfaction, life satisfaction, happiness, and self-rated anxiety. They studied different correlations in their research, such as those between work involvement and job satisfaction, intrinsic job motivation and job satisfaction, and perceived intrinsic job characteristics and job satisfaction. In particular, Warr et al. concluded that there exists a moderate association between total job satisfaction and total life satisfaction and happiness, with a less strong, but significant association with self-rated anxiety.
4. Mirvis and Lawler (1984) [22] found in their study that Quality of working life was related with satisfaction with wages, hours and working conditions, describing the "essentials of a good quality of work life" as; safe work environment, equitable wages, equal employment opportunities and opportunities for advancement.

STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF WORK LIFE :

The strategies for improvement in QWL include self managed work teams, job redesign and enrichment, effective leadership and supervisory behavior, career development alternative work

schedules, job security, administrative or organizational justice and participating management.1.

Self-managed work teams :

These are also called autonomous work groups or integrated work teams. These work teams are formed with 10 to 20 employees who plan, coordinate and control the activities of the team, with the help of a team leader, who is one among team.

Each team performs all activities including selecting their people. Each team perform all activities including selecting their people. Each team has authority to make decisions and regulate team performs all activities including selecting their people.

Each team has authority to make decisions and regulate the activities. Group as a whole, is accountable for the success or failure. Salaries and fixed both on the basis of individual and group achievement.

Job redesign and enrichment - Narrow jobs can be combined into larger units of accomplishment. Jobs are redesigned with a view to enriching them to satisfy higher other human needs

Effective leadership and supervisory behavior - For effective leadership and supervisory behavior style of managerial gird is suitable.

Career development - Provision for career planning, communicating & counseling the employees about the career opportunities career path, education and development and for second careers should be made.

Alternative work schedules - Provision for flexible working hours, parttime Employment's, job sharing and reduced workweek should be made.

Job security - This is the employee's list of the priority. It should be adequately taken care off.

Improving the Quality of Work Life :

Quality of Work Life efforts generally try to instill in employees the feelings of security, equity, pride, ownership, autonomy, responsibility and flexibility. They try to treat employees in a fair and supportive way, to open up communication channels at all levels, to offers employees opportunities to participate in decision affecting

them, and to empower them to deliver results independent using their talents fully. In order to improve the quality of work life, the following needs to be strengthened:

- Employment Conditions (safety, health, physical Environment).
- Equitable Rewards (pay, incentives, benefits, services)
- Job Security
- Enhancing the Self-Esteem of people
- Participative climate and team spirit
- Training to employees, managers, and Supervisors so that they share the vision, values and culture of the organization
- Autonomy to draw resources and deliver results
- Recognition for work done, followed by rewards so as to encourage commitments and belongingness
- Job redesign and job enrichment
- Open and transparent management style
- An atmosphere of trust and open communication

CONCLUSION:

The study found that there is a high level of satisfaction among the employees regarding the Quality of Work life. The factors determining the satisfaction with the quality of work life in the organization were “Adequate Income & Fair Compensation, Safe & healthy working conditions, Opportunities to use & develop human capacity, Opportunity for career growth, Social integration in the work force, Constitutionalism in work organization, Eminence of Work Life and Social relevance of work, Cordial relationship with employees and superiors, and remedy for the grievance and performance appraisal. All these factors are positively correlated with the quality of work life, Adequate training and development programs should be provided to the employees for an effective increase in the performance and attitude levels

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हिन्दी

उत्तरशती के हिन्दी उपन्यास साहित्य में सामाजिक बोध

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समाज के परम्परागत स्वरूप में पुरुष और स्त्री के अस्तित्व की भिन्न-भिन्न विचारधाराएँ मान्य रही हैं। पितृ सत्तात्मक समाज में स्त्री की अपेक्षा पुरुष को विशेष महत्व मिला है। नवीन परिवेश एवं व्यक्ति स्वातंत्र्य की भावना ने स्त्री पुरुष के मध्य भी पारस्परिक स्पर्धा को जन्म दिया। हिन्दी उपन्यासों में इसकी यथावत अभिव्यक्ति हुई है। व्यक्ति के महत्व की प्रतिष्ठा हेतु हिन्दी उपन्यासों में मुख्य रूप से दो विचारधाराओं का प्रतिपादन हुआ है। एक प्रत्यक्ष विचारधारा जिसमें समाज को गौण रूप में स्वीकार कर व्यक्ति स्वातंत्र्य का विरोधी माना गया। दूसरी परोक्ष, जहाँ समाज के प्रति प्रत्यक्ष रूप से अस्वीकृति न होकर विभिन्न कर्मों, घटनाओं के माध्यम से परम्परागत सामाजिक मूल्यों के प्रति विरोध अभिव्यक्त हुआ है।

आधुनिक परिवेश के प्रभाव स्वरूप सामाजिक मूल्य तेजी से परिवर्तित होने लगे। इस परिवर्तन के फलस्वरूप व्यक्ति की विचारधारा भी प्रभावित हुई और वह समाज के बनाये नियम-कानूनों का उल्लंघन कर अपने विद्रोही व्यक्तित्व को स्थापित करने लगा। साथ ही समाज के प्रति आक्रोश को अभिव्यक्त करते हुए उस पर सीधी चोट की है। 'बूंद और समुद्र' उपन्यास में 'महिपाल' समाज के प्रति विद्रोह की भावना अभिव्यक्त करते हुए कहता है - "अपनी जिम्मेदारियों को सदियों तक अदा करने के बाद इंसान ने इस चेतना का दर्शन किया कि उसके समाज का एक छोटा सा अंश उसका भाग्य विधायक बना हुआ है। यह दर्शन मिलते ही उसका भाग्य बदल गया, उसका कर्म बदल गया। आज उसके भाग्य में उन पुरानी परिस्थितियों के खिलाफ संघर्ष करना बड़ा है।" सामाजिक परम्पराओं से जड़ अभिशप्त जीवन वर्तमान पीढ़ी को स्वीकार नहीं फलस्वरूप उससे विद्रोह करना उसकी नियति बन चुकी है।

'पीली आँधी' की 'सोमा' समाज के प्रति विद्रोह का स्वर बुलंद करते हुए अपने व्यक्तिगत जीवन में समाज की दखलदाजी बर्दाश्त नहीं करती और अपने पति गौतम से कहती है - "समाज को, तुम्हारे इस समाज को, हमारे बारे में सोचने की फुर्सत भी है? तुम किस समाज की बात कर रहे हो? वह जिनसे तुम पार्टियों में मिलते हो? वह जो कला मन्दिर में बैठकर तालियाँ बजाता है? वह जो न्यू मार्केट में शापिंग करता है? वह समाज नहीं गौतम। वह तो बस पैसे वालों का समूह है, एक जल्था, हवा में उड़ता हुआ पेड़। अपने आसपास के माहौल से कटा हुआ, जमीन खोजता हुआ।" यह मान्यता घर करती जा रही है कि समाज जिसे मान्यता देता है वह सत्य नहीं है। सत्य तो इन सबसे परे एक विशेष परिस्थिति है। क्योंकि समाज अपने आप में सम्पूर्ण नहीं होता वह तो मानव द्वारा निर्मित एक व्यवस्था मात्र है। व्यक्ति पर कोई दायित्व नहीं है। न समाज का न संसार का। प्रत्येक व्यक्ति अपने आप में पूर्ण है।

उत्तरशती के हिन्दी उपन्यासों में इस प्रकार की विचारधारा का क्रमिक विकास मिलता है। समाज सापेक्ष व्यक्ति के स्थान पर समाज निरपेक्ष व्यक्ति की स्थापना के प्रति सजग रहा है। यहाँ समष्टि के स्थान पर व्यष्टि की स्थापना हेतु समाज के प्रति विरोध प्रत्यक्ष न होकर धर्म, रीति-रिवाज, परम्परा, संस्कार आदि मूल्यों के प्रति विद्रोह में प्रतिफलित हुआ है। इस सन्दर्भ में 'सूरज का सातवाँ घोड़ा' के मणिक मुल्ला का कथन दृष्टव्य है - "वास्तव में आर्थिक ढाँचा हमारे मन पर इतना अजब सा प्रभाव डालता है कि मन की सारी भावनाएँ उससे स्वाधीन नहीं हो पाती और हम जैसे लोग जो न उच्चवर्ग के हैं, न निम्नवर्ग के, उनके यहाँ रूढ़ियाँ परम्पराएँ, मर्यादाएँ भी ऐसी पुरानी और

विषाक्त हैं कि कुल मिलाकर हम सभी पर ऐसा प्रभाव पड़ता है कि हम यंत्र मात्र रह जाते हैं । हमारे अन्दर उदार और ऊँचे सपने खत्म हो जाते हैं और एक अजब सी जड़ मूर्च्छना हम पर छा जाती है ।³ अतः आवश्यकता इस बात की है कि—“उस व्यवस्था द्वारा लादी गयी सारी नैतिक विकृति को भी अस्वीकार करे और उसके द्वारा आरोपित सारी झूठी मर्यादाओं को भी ।”⁴ इस प्रकार परम्परागत समाज व्यवस्था द्वारा थोपी गयी रूढ़ियों एवं संस्कारों का विरोध कर व्यक्ति प्रतिष्ठा को उत्तरशती के उपन्यासों में प्रमुखता से अभिव्यक्त किया गया है ।

‘सारा आकाश’ में आर्थिक यंत्रणाओं के मध्य घुटता संयुक्त परिवार और टूटते व्यक्तित्व का निरूपण है । ‘सारा आकाश’ का ‘धीरज’ अकेले आठ—दस व्यक्तियों के संयुक्त परिवार की जिम्मेदारियों को निभाते—निभाते टूट चुका है — “हमारी जिन्दगी तो सिर्फ इसी काम के लिए बनी है कि बैल की तरह कमाएँ और इस गड़ढे में डालते रहें ।”⁵ परिवार में सर्वत्र मृत्यु का अवसाद है । आर्थिक तंगी के कारण समस्त परिवार में कलह का वातावरण व्याप्त है । ऐसी स्थिति में प्रगतिशील विचारों के ‘शिरीष’ का दृष्टिकोण एकमात्र उपाय सिद्ध हो सकता है । उसके अनुसार — “इस संयुक्त परिवार की परम्परा को तोड़ना ही होगा— संयुक्त परिवार का शाब्दिक अर्थ चाहे कितना ही महान हो, उसका सबसे बड़ा दोष यह होता है कि परिवार का कोई सदस्य अपने व्यक्तित्व का विकास नहीं कर पाता । सारा समय या तो समस्याएँ बनाने में या बनी बनाई समस्याओं को सुलझाने में जाता है । लड़ाई—झगड़ा, खींचतान, बदला, ग्लानि सब मिलाकर वातावरण ऐसा विषैला और दमघोंटू बना रहता है कि सांस नहीं ले सके ।”⁶ ‘सारा आकाश’ के इस संयुक्त परिवार में परिवार के प्रति किसी भी सदस्य की आस्था नहीं है । हर एक सदस्य परम्परागत मर्यादा और सामाजिक प्रतिष्ठा को बनाए रखने के लिए अपने व्यक्तित्व का बलिदान कर रहा है । वर्तमान समय में व्यक्ति जाग्रत है । परिणाम स्वरूप वह किसी पर निर्भर न रहकर आर्थिक स्वतंत्रता चाहता है आर्थिक रूप से स्वतंत्र व्यक्ति अपनी किसी भी इच्छा या आकांक्षा की पूर्ति में रूकावट बर्दाश्त नहीं करता । संयुक्त परिवार में अधिकांशतः वही होता है फलस्वरूप व्यक्ति परिवार से पृथक होने का निर्णय ले लेता है । विचारों में मतभेद व सामंजस्य का अभाव भी संयुक्त परिवार के सदस्यों के बीच संघर्ष को बढ़ावा देता है । ‘यह पथ बंधु था’ में संयुक्त परिवार के कमाऊ सदस्य स्वतंत्र हो जाना चाहते हैं । पिता इस स्थिति से परेशान होकर कहते हैं — “अब दुनिया भर के यह छल—प्रपंच मेरी समझ में नहीं आते । होगा, जिसे रहना हो रहे । नाक भौं सिकोड़ कर किसी को रहने की जरूरत नहीं । जहाँ सींग समाए वहीं जाए ।”⁷ अब पिता भी ऐसे परिवार को बाँधकर नहीं रखना चाहते जहाँ सदस्यों में एकता की भावना न रहकर व्यक्तिगत स्वार्थ उभरने लगे हों ।

‘पीली आँधी’ में परम्परागत मारगंवाड़ी समाज के

पुरातन विचारों एवं संस्कारों वाला परिवार पश्चिमी सभ्यता के प्रभाववश जमीन पर बैठकर भोजन करने की बजाय डायनिंग टेबल पर भोजन करना आधुनिक होने की पहचान मानता है, इसलिए ऐसी व्यवस्था की जाती है कि परोसते वक्त नौकर को बहू — बेटियों का कंधा न छू जाए — “बड़े से हाल में सोलह कुर्सियों वाली डायनिंग टेबल, यू शैप की । बीच में नौकर घूम—घूम कर सबके सामने भोजन परोस सकता था । ‘सोमा’ को लगा अंग्रेजी और हिन्दुस्तानी तरीके का अच्छा मिक्सचर है ।”⁸ शिक्षा और परिवेश में आयी नवीनता के फलस्वरूप व्यक्ति के खान—पान एवं रहन—सहन में भी बदलाव दृष्टिगत होने लगा ।

सामाजिक प्रक्रिया के सन्दर्भ में समाजशास्त्रियों की दो प्रकार की धारणाएँ विद्यमान रही हैं । प्रथम यह कि सामाजिक परिवर्तन की प्रक्रिया एक चक्र की भाँति चलती है । जिस प्रकार दिन के पश्चात् रात एवं रात के पश्चात् दिन आता है, ठीक उसी प्रकार समाज में परिवर्तन का चक्र चलता रहता है । समाज बनता है, बिगड़ता है, फिर बनता है । सभ्यताओं का उदय, अन्त एवं पुनः उदय होता है । इस परिवर्तन के सन्दर्भ में दूसरी धारणा यह है कि सामाजिक परिवर्तन चक्र में न चलकर एक सीधी दिशा में विकास की ओर बढ़ता है । यहाँ विकास का अर्थ उन्नति से नहीं है । विकास अर्थात् अपने स्थान से बढ़ना । यह बढ़ना आगे भी हो सकता है और पीछे भी । हमारा समाज सतत् विकसित तो हुआ है पर यह कहना कठिन होगा कि उसने सदा ही उन्नति की है ।

युगानुकूल समाज व्यवस्था में परिवर्तन होता रहा है । आदिमयुग का समाज आज नहीं है । प्राचीन परम्पराएँ, रीति—रिवाज, संस्कार, वर्ण व्यवस्था आदि वर्तमान समय में अपने आदिम रूप से भिन्न स्वरूप में दृष्टिगत होते हैं । सामाजिक परिवर्तन की प्रक्रिया अत्यंत धीमी होती है । रीति—रिवाज, जाति, धर्म आदि में परिवर्तन आते—आते सैकड़ों वर्ष लग जाते हैं । अतः इस परिवर्तन की प्रक्रिया को स्पष्ट रूप से देखा नहीं जा सकता । परन्तु रहन—सहन, खान—पान, फैशन, आचरण, व्यवहार आदि में परिवर्तन अपेक्षाकृत शीघ्र होता है । उत्तरशती का उपन्यास साहित्य इस परिवर्तन को सामाजिक बोध के विविध आयामों के साथ चित्रित करता है ।

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